

D 3.3

Report on metrics, thresholds
and minimum requirements
for sustainability indicators.

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TUB	Technische Universität Berlin
UNITELMA	Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma
UNI	Ente Italiano di Normazione
AUA	Geononiko Panepistimion Athinon
USC	Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
NOVA	Institut for politische und Okologische Innovation GMBH
BB	Better Biomass
BAM	Bundesanstalt fuer Materialforschung und Pruefung
RSB	Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association
ISEAL	Iseal Alliance

Abbreviations

BMS	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System
D.X.Y	Deliverable y from work package x
FEFAC	European Feed Manufacturers' Federation
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
GHG	Greenhouse gas emissions
GSSI	Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative
IAT	STAR ProBio Integrated Assessment Tool
iLUC	Indirect land use change
ISCC	International Sustainability & Carbon Certification
ITC	International Trade Center
LCA	Life cycle assessment
MR	Minimum Requirement
MS	Monitoring system
N	No
N/A	Not applicable
PEFC	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RSB	Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials
CSLs	Certification Schemes and Labels
SCT	STAR ProBio Sustainability Certification Tools
SSCI	Sustainable Supply Chain Initiative
SSCT	Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool
WP	Work package
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature
Y	Yes

The primary goal of the STAR4BBS project is to facilitate the alignment of current sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs) requirements and criteria to fully leverage their potential to support a successful transition to sustainable bio-based economy. To this end, in collaboration with two sister projects (HARMONITOR and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED), the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System (BMS) is being developed.

This system is composed of the following three levels: system, content and outcome. The System Level focuses on operational requirements of the certification scheme, to assess its robustness, governance and credibility. The Content Level covers specific requirements in line with EU environmental, social, economic and circularity priorities and targets. Finally, the Outcome Level measures the impact and effectiveness of the application of these schemes and labels. In addition, it includes the component evaluation structure, which refers to the way in which the data collected about each CSL will be analysed and assessed.

Each level of the BMS (in particular, the system and the content level) includes a comprehensive set of indicators. This deliverable, based on the analysis of the European legal framework (e.g. RED II and the EU Green Claims Directive) and on the current coverage of key areas by CSLs, complemented with stakeholders' inputs, proposes a first selection of minimum requirements ("need to have" indicators) and related metrics for the content and system levels.

In total, 21, 13, 2 and 7 minimum requirements are proposed to be included as minimum requirements in the BMS, for the environmental, circularity, economic and social pillars, respectively. For the system level, in total 29 requirements are proposed as "need to have" requirements.

These proposed minimum requirements aim to prioritize crucial criteria for CSLs, while remaining adaptable to changes based on stakeholder feedback and policy updates.

In recent years, Sustainability Certification Schemes and labels (CSLs) have emerged as a prominent force in the establishment of standards and governance within the framework of sustainable development, establishing themselves as an authoritative source of reference on the topic (Auld, Gulbrandsen, & McDermott, 2008). One of the main reasons for this is that when state organisations are not able to solve a problem, the private sector is compelled to assume a role in its resolution.

In this way, this has led to the rise of environmental organisations, as evidenced by the emergence of the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) scheme, which originated from the dissatisfaction of the ecological advocacy groups with the Rio de Janeiro Earth Summit regarding forestry. However, it is important to note that, given the voluntary nature of CSLs, these standards must be distinguished from mandatory legal regulations (Tröster and Hiete, 2018).

CSLs include a set of criteria and requirements that should be met in order to obtain certification. Thus, based on the above, it is essential that these criteria and requirements are aligned with policy priorities and that can facilitate achieving them, thereby contributing to sustainable development within the framework of the bioeconomy and demonstrating their effectiveness. It is, therefore, of the utmost importance that CSLs standards are designed in a way that ensures complementarity and alignment, rather than substitution, with the aforementioned policies (Mori et al., 2016).

Under this premise, the STAR4BSS project aims to contribute to the harmonisation of the requirements and criteria of certification schemes and labels. In pursuing this objective it joined effort with two other EU Horizon projects as explained in Box 1.

Box 1

The **STAR4BBS** project (Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems) is a Coordination and Support action, which addressed the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07: *International and EU sustainability certification schemes for bio-based systems*. Two other projects – **HARMONITOR** (Harmonisation and monitoring platform for certification schemes and labels to advance the sustainability of bio-based systems) led by the SQ Consult, and **SUSTCERT4BIOBASED** (Sustainability Certification for Biobased Systems) led by the Stichting Wageningen Research, were also awarded to address the same call. The three sister projects work together in the implementation of different joint activities. One of them is the development of a BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System, of which the initial proposal, accepted by the EU officials in June 2023, is included in the Annex of *D4.1 Concept of the monitoring system*.

The goal of the three sister projects working together to develop a BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System (BMS) is to reduce confusion, divergences, and mistrust among stakeholders by creating a harmonized, overarching system. This would bring coherence to the space and clarity for policymakers driving the transition to a bioeconomy in the EU. Working together would allow the projects to build on each other's knowledge and experience, subjecting the BMS to a higher level of scrutiny, and maximizing the effective use of resources. The BMS would streamline stakeholder consultations and reduce fatigue while eliminating competition among the three projects and maximizing the synergies and impacts of the results. The creation of a BMS will require greater coordination, but it is believed to be feasible and

worthwhile to work together to provide a more comprehensive and detailed tool, covering a wide range of bio-based sectors and products.

The monitoring system incorporates a comprehensive set of indicators aimed at gathering crucial information on the effectiveness and robustness of certification schemes and labels. These indicators are structured into three levels:

I) System Level: These indicators focus on the characteristics of the certification scheme, including its governance and the development process of standards or labels.

II) Content Level: These indicators specify the requirements of the certification scheme concerning various EU environmental, social, economic, and circularity priorities and targets. Minimum requirements that all SCS and labels should adhere to will be defined with a life cycle perspective.

III) Outcome Level: The outcome indicators measure the impact generated by the certification schemes and labels. They encompass life-cycle assessment comparison indicators and continual improvement indicators.

An important element of the BMS is the evaluation structure, a part of an assessment system to implement proposed monitoring system. In this regard, this deliverable conducts a prioritization of the proposed requirements of the D3.2 (*D3.2 Report on additional indicators of monitoring system*) not only considering the current criteria of the CSLs and MSs, but also including the current political perspective to strengthen and refine the results. This analysis will allow the development of a system of metrics that considers the enforceability of the requirements and provides recommendations for new metrics to the BMS, ensuring the presence of those fundamental MRs to guarantee its operational, environmental, circular, economic and social robustness.

This report comprises two principal sections. **Section 2** addresses content-level matters and is structured as follows: **Subsection 2.1** assesses the alignment of the Content-Level requirements proposed in D3.2 with the CSLs, monitoring systems and policies. **Subsection 2.2** categorises the requirements according to their frequency of occurrence in the previously analysed documents. **Subsection 2.3** proposes minimum requirements for selected indicators of D3.2. Finally, **Subsection 2.4** proposes potential metrics for quantifying the identified requirements.

The **Section 3** on System Level is comprised of the principal part, introducing the minimum requirements and previously developed indicators for the system level. It is then followed by two subsections: **Subsection 3.1** deals with the methodology for determining the minimum requirements of the system level, focusing on stakeholder feedback, comparisons with existing tools, and policy benchmarking. **Subsection 3.2** presents the results, outlining the proposal of minimum requirements and how they were benchmarked against variables, with a focus on coverage and gaps.

2.1 Alignment of D 3.2 requirements with standards and policies.

In deliverable D3.2 *Report on additional indicators of monitoring system*, an in-depth analysis of 19 certification schemes and 12 monitoring systems was carried out. The objective of this analysis was to identify and select the environmental, circular, economic and social requirements that a bio-based value chain must fulfil in order to meet sustainability criteria. Gaps in these standards were also assessed and addressed by analysing relevant grey literature, mainly due to the lack of requirements in the circularity pillar. All the aforementioned information, including some of the LCA indicators identified in D3.1, was included into an Excel spreadsheet, forming the Content-Level matrix, which was appended to D3.2. The requirements set out in this matrix constituted the basis for the analyses proposed in this document.

However, in order to be able to assess the sustainability of a process or value chain, it is essential to establish feasible, objective and fair assessment criteria that allow the users of the BMS to extract relevant information on the strengths and weaknesses of the different sustainability pillars analysed. In this sense, it is necessary to establish levels of rigour or priorities among the requirements identified in the previous deliverable to propose a set of minimum sustainability requirements (MR) to be considered in the BMS.

In order to identify these MRs, the degree of representativeness of the requirements proposed in the Content-Level Matrix within the certification schemes, monitoring systems and European policies has been thoroughly assessed. Thus, based on the results of the analysis, three levels of requirements are defined according to the degree of enforceability (which requirements should be included as mandatory to ensure the robustness of the standard and which can be considered as optional) associated with them (minimum, intermediate and advanced requirements), as can be seen in **Figure 1**. The analysis of these standards and policies and their results will be detailed in depth in the following sections of the document.

Figure 1. Levels of requirement based on their associated enforceability.

The analysis of the aforementioned documents made it possible to count, for each requirement, the number of policies or standards that are aligned with it, from which the percentage of representativeness of each requirement was calculated and assigned a level of enforceability. **Table 1** shows the distribution of the percentiles used to assign minimum, intermediate and advanced levels to the different requirements according to their frequency of occurrence in the documents.

Table 1. Distribution of the criteria in the different levels selected on the basis of their frequency of occurrence in the policies and standards.

Level	Normalised percentage¹ of frequency in CSLs and MSs
Minimum	100 – 50 %
Intermediate	50 – 20 %
Advanced	< 20 %

¹The percentage was calculated as the number of documents aligned with the requirement divided by the total number of documents analysed for each case (CSLs, MSs and European policies) and normalised to the maximum value.

2.1.1 Alignment study of the D3.2 criteria with the standards

During the analysis carried out in D3.2 the information collected was harmonised, resulting in a monitoring system with a holistic approach, covering the different sectors of the bioeconomy and avoiding duplication of elements. This monitoring system with the final set of indicators for the Content and the System Level was provided as Excels attached to the report.

In this way, the large amount of information analysed for the previous deliverable also makes it possible to carry out a frequency analysis of the different requirements selected among the standards analysed. In other words, an assessment of the number of CSLs and the number of MSs they include in order to analyse the sustainability of the bio-based value chain.

This frequency of occurrence of the proposed requirements among the different standards allows a categorisation according to the following: the greater the number of standards referring to a particular requirement, the greater the enforceability associated with it.

The selection of these certification schemes and monitoring systems identified in WP1 (D1.2 and D1.4 respectively) was based on the same criteria applied in the previous deliverable. Consequently, the frequency analysis was carried out on the selection of 19 CSLs and 12 MSs previously assessed.

Tables B.1-B.8 of Appendix B show the identifiers (requirement codes) of the proposed content-level requirements and the standards in which they are included, indicated by a "green cell" for the environmental, circular, economic and social pillars respectively. Two summary tables were prepared for each pillar separately, one for the CSLs and one for the MSs, resulting in a total of 8 frequency analysis tables for the different requirements.

On the basis of the above, the minimum criteria were selected, taking into account the most frequent criteria in the standards analysed, which, as mentioned in Deliverable 3.2,

provide a complete overview of the different raw materials, products and stages of the value chains to be certified.

Furthermore, the proposed analysis has also allowed to assess the representativeness of the requirements of the Content-Level matrix in certification schemes (**Figure 2**) and monitoring systems (**Figure 3**). In general terms, both figures show that no CSL or MS present a comprehensive approach that allows them to cover almost all aspects related to the sustainability of bio-based value chains, and in all cases analysed there are important gaps that demonstrate the relevance and importance of the proposed harmonisation.

With regard to certification schemes, **Figure 2.a** shows the representativeness of the requirements of the environmental pillar in these schemes. In this way, the Key Areas that include the largest number of the proposed requirements and thus cover most of the related sustainability aspects associated with them are, in order, Hazardous Substances, Biodiversity and Soil. In addition, the CSLs also highlight to a large extent the need to train operators in sustainability practices (Generic). On the other hand, the environmental aspects related to the Key Areas Air, Natural Resources, Climate Change and Water were found to be less relevant by the CSLs.

On the other hand, **Figure 2.b** shows the circularity requirements of the Content-Level matrix included in the CSLs. Although it could be observed that some of the certification schemes include sustainability criteria regarding product design and the circularity of production processes, as indicated in the previous deliverable. Circularity is not yet well described and included in the standards, so it is not possible to develop a prioritisation as was done for the environmental pillar.

Figure 2.c shows the representativeness of the requirements proposed for the economic pillar in the schemes. As can be seen, most CSLs do not include aspects of economic sustainability, so it is not possible to develop a prioritisation based on these criteria. Consequently, the selection of minimum requirements for both this pillar and the circularity pillar requires an extension of the analysis.

On the other hand, **Figure 2.d** shows the proposed social requirements included in the analysed schemes. The main area that stands out is the inclusion of sustainability aspects with respect to workers, with a high degree of representativeness of the requirements in most of the standards. In addition, Local Communities are also significantly included in the scope of certification. Other Key Areas, such as Consumers, Value Chain Actors and Society, are present in the CSLs and have a remarkable representativeness in them, but still lack sufficient requirements to ensure correct performance in the context of social sustainability.

With regard to monitoring systems, **Figure 3.a** shows the environmental requirements included in the Content-Level matrix. The Key Areas of greatest importance in this case are Soil, Water, Biodiversity and Hazardous. Thus, except for the environmental requirements for water, which are more relevant in the case of the MSs, the results obtained are practically analogous to those of the CSLs.

Figure 3.b plots the circularity requirements included in the MSs. Compared to what was concluded in the certification schemes, the monitoring systems include aspects related

to the circularity of processes and the design of materials and products; however, new circular business models or requirements related to the last stages of the life cycle of products (disposal, recycling, reuse...) are still not taken into account in a significant way, which does not allow them to be prioritised objectively in line with the interests of the European community.

On the other hand, **Figure 3.c** shows the economic requirements included in the MSs analysed. Once again, although the Key Area of Profitability is more relevant to the CSLs, in general terms the MSs show significant shortcomings in terms of requirements to achieve economic sustainability within the value chain, which in turn makes it difficult to prioritise the minimum requirements that standards should meet to ensure this objective.

Finally, **Figure 3.d** plots the representativeness of social requirements in the MS. Similarly to the CSLs, the Key Area with the greatest importance is that of Workers, followed by Local Community, with similar gaps within the pillar.

These analyses show the need to include new requirements in the CSLs and the MSs, which will allow them to meet the environmental challenges that the future European horizon implies in terms of sustainability. The conservation and restoration of ecosystem services play a fundamental role in carbon storage and the recovery of marine and terrestrial biodiversity, the conservation of soil and water and the responsible use of their resources could help to achieve a fair and sustainable development of society and the reuse of resources to reduce emissions and air pollution, all with the aim of achieving climate neutrality by 2050.

In addition, regarding the main objective of this study, based on the above, it has also been possible to observe the priorities of the standards, which serve as a basis for defining minimum requirements based on the current criteria for them, as detailed in **Subsection 2.2** of the document. However, in order to identify the minimum requirements in the pillars covering the aspects of sustainability not yet covered by the standards, mainly circularity and economic aspects, it is necessary to extend the study, as proposed in the following section, by analysing European policies and objectives.

Figure 2. Alignment between requirements and certification schemes per Key Area. Dark colours represent the requirements included in the certification scheme, light colour the total amount of requirements of the Key Area. A, B, C, D for the environmental, circularity, economic and social pillars respectively.

Figure 3. Alignment between requirements and monitoring systems per Key Area. Dark colours represent the requirements included in the monitoring system, light colour the total amount of requirements of the Key Area. A, B, C, D for the environmental, circularity, economic and social pillars respectively.

2.1.2 Alignment of the proposed Content-Level requirements with the European policies of D1.1

As detailed in the previous section, there are gaps in the current sustainability standards in relation to the achievement of the objectives proposed by the European Union in terms of sustainability. Consequently, in order to prioritise the requirements proposed in the D3.2 Content-Level matrix according to the goals and demands required by the EU, an analysis has been made of the policy initiatives and directives promoted in recent years, assessing their trends and priorities for achieving sustainable growth by reducing the pressure on natural resources.

The most relevant directives within the STAR4BBS project framework were analysed in WPI and included in D1.1 'Report on policy sustainability targets', where a list of 29 policies published since 2018 was proposed. After an internal meeting with the partners of Nova-Institut für politische und Ökologische Innovation GmbH (NOVA) in charge of this deliverable, it was decided to reduce the number of policies to be analysed for the proposed prioritisation study to 15, excluding those related to the energy sector and others whose content would not contribute significant information to the main objective of the analysis.

Tables C.1-C.4 of Appendix C list the 15 policies analysed to assess their alignment with the proposed requirements for the environmental, circular economic and social pillars respectively. The analysis carried out is analogous to that proposed for the CSLs and MSs, marking with a 'green cell' those requirements that are included in or aligned with the objectives of the policies assessed. This study makes it possible to prioritise the requirements into minimum, intermediate and advanced based on the degree of enforceability reflected in the documents.

On the other hand, **Figure 4** shows the representativeness of the proposed content-level requirements, grouped by Key Area, in the policies analysed. It can be seen that, in general terms, the policies cover most of the requirements that bio-based value chains need to fulfil in order to meet environmental, circular, economic and social sustainability criteria. In fact, with respect to the standards assessment carried out previously, there is a significant degree of alignment for most of the Key Areas that extends to the economic and circularity pillars, which allows the policy frequency analysis to be used to prioritise those requirements that are more demanding under the policy criteria.

In more detail, **Figure 4.a** shows the representativeness of the environmental pillar requirements in the policies. In this case, it can be seen that most of the policies are aligned with the sustainability criteria set for the Key Area of Climate Change, demonstrating that the integrated approach proposed for the Content-Level covers most of the aspects related to it to a good degree, in contrast to the standards assessed. In order, the policies also prioritise environmental requirements related to the Key Areas Generic, Soil, Natural Resources, Hazardous Substances and Biodiversity. In addition, the other Key Areas are significantly represented in the policies, although to a lesser extent than those mentioned above.

On the other hand, **Figure 4.b** plots the circularity requirements aligned with policies. In contrast to the standards in the previous section, in this case all Key Areas show a similar degree of representativeness of their requirements, which is significant enough to analyse policy priorities and identify the minimum requirements for achieving sustainable circularity performance by bio-based value chains.

Furthermore, it is also interesting to note that, although the European regulatory framework has made significant efforts regarding the application of circularity criteria with policy initiatives such as the 'Circular Economy Action Plan', the 'Waste Framework Directive' and the 'Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation', analysed in this document, there is still significant room for improvement as shown in the graph below. Thus, it would be interesting to consider some of the Intermediate and Advanced circularity requirements listed in **Subsection 2.2**, which are currently not endowed with a significant degree of relevance, for the development of future policy initiatives.

On the other hand, regarding the representativeness of economic requirements, **Figure 4.c** shows that the policies also include sustainability criteria related to these. The Key Areas whose requirements are most aligned with the policy objectives are Economic Risks and Long-term Investment; however, although in this case the coverage of the pillar is considerably higher than that of the standards, the results show a significant lack of economic sustainability requirements for value chains, possibly because their inclusion could jeopardise or limit the development of activities in a free market.

Finally, **Figure 4.d** shows the representativeness of the social requirements of the Content-Level proposed in D3.2 in the policies. In this case, in contrast to the standards, the requirements with the highest relevance correspond to those of the Key Areas of Consumers and Society. Furthermore, although the policies are also aligned with the requirements of the Workers, Value Chain Actors and Local Community areas, in general terms, the results show that a significant part of the requirements associated with those are not included in the directives.

Based on the above, the analysis of the policy initiatives has shown a significant representativeness of the proposed requirements within the four pillars, thus allowing their prioritisation based on enforceability and current sustainability policy objectives. Furthermore, the holistic approach proposed in the previous deliverable, in which sustainability requirements from several relevant sources have been harmonised, reveals the existence of certain aspects that are not generally covered by standards and policies. Consequently, it is interesting to consider the inclusion of some of the requirements not categorised as MR in **Subsection 2.2** in future standards and policies, with the aim of achieving a robust sustainable development framework with a multi-criteria approach (environmental, circular, economic and social) that considers all aspects of sustainability.

Figure 4. Alignment between requirements and policies per Key Area. Dark colours represent the requirements included in the respective policy, light colour the total amount of requirements of the Key Area. A, B, C, D for the environmental, circularity, economic and social pillars respectively.

As shown in the previous section, although the standards do not include significant aspects related to circularity and economic requirements, their priorities in the environmental and social pillars are similar to those observed in the policies. In order to improve the analytical process and to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the sustainability trends and objectives inherent in the documents under consideration, a joint assessment of these documents has been carried out. This assessment will include an evaluation of the priorities identified within each sub-area, with the aim of selecting the intermediate and advanced MRs, as outlined in the following section.

Consequently, **Figure 5-Figure 8** show the representativeness of the requirements of the Content-Level matrix grouped by Sub-Areas for the different pillars. These show that the average percentage of requirements in the set of standards and policies is between 6 and 30%, with the lowest percentage corresponding to economic requirements and the highest to environmental requirements. Thus, although concrete measures are currently being implemented in terms of environmental sustainability, the analysis shows that there is still a long way to achieve the objectives of the four pillars studied.

In general terms for the environmental pillar (**Figure 5**) it can be seen that the priority requirements are related to: the reduction of GHG emissions (41 % of representativeness), the adoption of climate change mitigation (32 %) and adaptation (35 %) measures or strategies, the conservation and improvement of water (33 %) and soil quality (36 %), the establishment of plans for the conservation and monitoring of biodiversity (37 %), the sustainable use of natural resources (33 % for abiotic and 27% for biotic), the minimisation of impacts on human health (48 %), the reduction of the use of hazardous substances as well as their management (31 %) and the need to train operators in sustainability practices (48 %).

Regarding the circularity pillar (**Figure 6**), standards and policies prioritise those requirements related to: increased use of recycled or renewable materials in the production process (26 % of representativeness), improved efficiency and energy savings in the process (24 %), and the application of circularity criteria in product design (22 %, more durable, repairable, recyclable...).

On the other hand, the economic pillar (**Figure 7**) demonstrates minimal demand for compliance with any particular requirement, as previously stated. However, among those proposed, a greater prioritisation was observed for the identification of investment of resources in innovation and sustainability strategies. This is an area of great interest to companies today, as the EU is allocating significant resources to this end in most of the European directives and initiatives that open up and expand markets related to sustainability. On the other hand, it is also important to measure the economic viability of the process in the long term.

Finally, with regard to the social pillar (**Figure 8**), it can be observed that the most relevant requirements are those demanding: equal opportunities without discrimination and guaranteeing the health and safety of workers, good working

conditions, compliance with employee rights, ensuring food supply, respecting and clarifying property rights and contributing to the development of local communities.

Figure 5. Representativeness of environmental pillar requirements in standards and policy initiatives/ Directives

Figure 6. Representativeness of circularity pillar requirements in standards and policy initiatives/ Directives

Figure 7. Representativeness of economic pillar requirements in standards and policy initiatives/ Directives

Figure 8. Representativeness of social pillar requirements in standards and policy initiatives/ Directives

2.2 Identification of minimum, intermediate and advanced requirements according to standards and policies

Finally, based on the results of the analysis, each requirement was categorised according to its assigned level of enforceability based on alignment with the objectives and priorities of the standards and policies. To this end, the percentage of documents containing each pillar requirement was calculated as the number of documents containing it divided by the total number assessed in each case, i.e. by the total number of standards for the first analysis and by the total number of policies for the second.

Thus, if in the first analysis regarding certification schemes and monitoring systems a requirement A is included in 3 CSLs and 2 MSs, its percentage of inclusion in the standards is obtained as the sum of both (5) divided by those analysed in total (19 CSLs and 12 MSs), resulting in a representativeness of 16%. On the other hand, if the same requirement A is included in 9 of the 15 policies analysed, its representativeness with respect to these would be 60%. The values obtained for the analysis with respect to the standards and policies are shown in **Table 5** and **Table 7**, respectively.

After calculating the percentage of inclusion of each requirement in the documents, directly related to their enforceability for their prioritisation within the BMS, the values obtained were normalised with respect to the resulting maximum percentage within the pillar. Once these values were obtained, as shown in **Table 4** and **Table 6**, the requirements were categorised according to the level of enforceability associated with them. **Table 2** shows the distribution of percentiles used to assign Minimum, Intermediate and Advanced levels to the different requirements according to their frequency of occurrence among the documents.

Table 2. Distribution of the criteria in the different levels selected on the basis of their frequency of occurrence in the policies and standards.

Level	Normalised percentage¹ of frequency in CSLs and MS
Minimum	100 – 50 %
Intermediate	50 – 20 %
Advanced	< 20 %

¹ The percentage was calculated as the number of documents aligned with the requirement divided by the total number of documents analysed for each case (CSLs, MSs and European policies) and normalised to the maximum value.

Based on this in the analysis of the standards, a total of 26 Minimum requirements, 38 Intermediate and 22 Advanced were obtained. On the other hand, from the analysis of the policies, the number obtained were 41, 40 and 61 respectively. The distribution of requirements per pillar is shown in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Distribution of requirements by pillar based on their level of enforceability.

	Minimum		Intermediate		Advanced	
	Standards	Policies	Standards	Policies	Standards	Policies
Environmental	17	20	26	16	8	15
Circularity	-	13	-	8	-	14
Economic	-	2	-	5	-	14
Social	9	6	12	11	14	18

Table 5. Percentage of inclusion of the requirements of each sustainability pillar in the analysed certification schemes and monitoring systems

Environmental		Circularity		Economic		Social	
Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in standards						
EN-CC-1	32%	CR-EoLS-1	6%	E-ER-1	3%	SOC-CO-1	6%
EN-CC-2	39%	CR-EoLS-2	3%	E-ER-2	3%	SOC-CO-2	13%
EN-CC-3	19%	CR-EoLS-3	6%	E-ER-3	3%	SOC-CO-3	13%
EN-CC-4	3%	CR-EoLS-4	3%	E-ER-4	0%	SOC-LC-1	29%
EN-CC-5	10%	CR-EoLS-5	6%	E-ER-5	3%	SOC-LC-2	19%
EN-CC-6	10%	CR-EoLS-6	3%	E-P-1	0%	SOC-LC-3	10%
EN-CC-7	23%	CR-EoLS-7	6%	E-P-2	3%	SOC-LC-4	19%
EN-CC-8	6%	CR-EoLS-8	3%	E-LTI-1	3%	SOC-LC-5	35%
EN-A-1	16%	CR-EoLS-9	16%	E-LTI-2	6%	SOC-LC-6	16%
EN-A-2	16%	CR-EoLS-10	3%	E-LTI-3	3%	SOC-LC-7	13%
EN-A-3	13%	CR-EoLS-11	3%	E-LTI-4	6%	SOC-LC-8	13%
EN-A-4	10%	CR-CBM-1	3%	E-LTI-5	0%	SOC-LC-9	42%
EN-A-5	6%	CR-CBM-2	3%	E-LTI-6	3%	SOC-LC-10	6%
EN-W-1	45%	CR-G-1	3%	E-PRF-1	6%	SOC-LC-11	26%
EN-W-2	26%	CR-G-2	3%	E-PRF-2	3%	SOC-LC-12	19%
EN-W-3	3%	CR-PP-1	3%	E-PRF-3	0%	SOC-SO-1	3%
EN-W-4	19%	CR-PP-2	10%	E-PRF-4	3%	SOC-SO-2	3%
EN-W-5	26%	CR-PP-3	16%	E-PRF-5	3%	SOC-SO-3	23%
EN-W-6	23%	CR-PP-4	3%	E-PRF-6	3%	SOC-VCA-1	13%
EN-W-7	16%	CR-PP-5	10%	E-PRF-7	3%	SOC-VCA-2	16%
EN-W-8	32%	CR-PP-6	10%	E-PRF-8	3%	SOC-VCA-3	3%
EN-W-9	16%	CR-PP-7	10%			SOC-VCA-4	13%
EN-W-10	23%	CR-PP-8	3%			SOC-VCA-5	23%
EN-S-1	48%	CR-PP-9	3%			SOC-VCA-6	13%
EN-S-2	23%	CR-PP-10	3%			SOC-WO-1	55%
EN-S-3	26%	CR-PP-11	10%			SOC-WO-2	32%
EN-B-1	26%	CR-PP-12	29%			SOC-WO-3	6%
EN-B-2	42%	CR-PMD-1	3%			SOC-WO-4	68%
EN-B-3	32%	CR-PMD-2	3%			SOC-WO-5	58%
EN-B-4	42%	CR-PMD-3	3%			SOC-WO-6	55%
EN-B-5	23%	CR-PMD-4	13%			SOC-WO-7	55%
EN-B-6	29%	CR-PMD-5	6%			SOC-WO-8	29%
EN-B-7	35%	CR-PMD-6	3%			SOC-WO-9	65%
EN-B-8	23%	CR-PMD-7	10%			SOC-WO-10	29%
EN-B-9	35%	CR-PMD-8	13%			SOC-WO-11	61%
EN-B-10	29%						
EN-NR-1	23%						
EN-NR-2	16%						
EN-NR-3	6%						
EN-NR-4	29%						
EN-NR-5	23%						
EN-NR-6	16%						
EN-NR-7	16%						
EN-HS-1	55%						
EN-HS-2	13%						
EN-HS-3	45%						
EN-HS-4	26%						
EN-HS-5	23%						
EN-HS-6	48%						
EN-HS-7	13%						
EN-G-1	29%						

Table 4. Normalised inclusion percentage (based on the maximum pillar value, IP) of the requirements in certification schemes and monitoring systems. Ordered and prioritised as follows: Minimum Requirement if IP ≥ 50%, Intermediate if 50% < IP ≤ 20% and Advanced if IP < 20%. (NS – Not significant for prioritisation of requirements)

Environmental		Circularity		Economic		Social	
Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in standards						
EN-HS-1	100%	CR-PP-12	NS	E-LTI-2	NS	SOC-WO-4	100%
EN-S-1	88%	CR-PMD-4	NS	E-LTI-4	NS	SOC-WO-9	95%
EN-HS-6	88%	CR-PMD-8	NS	E-PRF-1	NS	SOC-WO-11	90%
EN-W-1	82%	CR-PMD-7	NS	E-PRF-2	NS	SOC-WO-5	86%
EN-HS-3	82%	CR-EoLS-9	NS	E-PRF-4	NS	SOC-WO-1	81%
EN-B-2	76%	CR-PP-3	NS	E-PRF-5	NS	SOC-WO-6	81%
EN-B-4	76%	CR-PMD-5	NS	E-PRF-6	NS	SOC-WO-7	81%
EN-CC-2	71%	CR-PP-2	NS	E-PRF-7	NS	SOC-LC-9	62%
EN-B-7	65%	CR-PP-5	NS	E-PRF-8	NS	SOC-LC-5	52%
EN-B-9	65%	CR-PP-6	NS	E-ER-1	NS	SOC-WO-2	48%
EN-CC-1	59%	CR-PP-7	NS	E-ER-2	NS	SOC-LC-1	43%
EN-W-8	59%	CR-PP-11	NS	E-ER-3	NS	SOC-WO-8	43%
EN-B-3	59%	CR-PMD-1	NS	E-ER-5	NS	SOC-WO-10	43%
EN-B-6	53%	CR-PMD-2	NS	E-P-2	NS	SOC-LC-11	38%
EN-B-10	53%	CR-PMD-3	NS	E-LTI-1	NS	SOC-SO-3	33%
EN-NR-4	53%	CR-PMD-6	NS	E-LTI-3	NS	SOC-VCA-5	33%
EN-G-1	53%	CR-EoLS-1	NS	E-LTI-6	NS	SOC-LC-2	29%
EN-W-2	47%	CR-EoLS-3	NS	E-ER-4	NS	SOC-LC-4	29%
EN-W-5	47%	CR-EoLS-5	NS	E-P-1	NS	SOC-LC-12	29%
EN-S-3	47%	CR-EoLS-7	NS	E-LTI-5	NS	SOC-LC-6	24%
EN-B-1	47%	CR-EoLS-2	NS	E-PRF-3	NS	SOC-VCA-2	24%
EN-HS-4	47%	CR-EoLS-4	NS			SOC-CO-2	19%
EN-CC-7	41%	CR-EoLS-6	NS			SOC-CO-3	19%
EN-W-6	41%	CR-EoLS-8	NS			SOC-LC-7	19%
EN-W-10	41%	CR-EoLS-10	NS			SOC-LC-8	19%
EN-S-2	41%	CR-EoLS-11	NS			SOC-VCA-1	19%
EN-B-5	41%	CR-CBM-1	NS			SOC-VCA-4	19%
EN-B-8	41%	CR-CBM-2	NS			SOC-VCA-6	19%
EN-NR-1	41%	CR-G-1	NS			SOC-LC-3	14%
EN-NR-5	41%	CR-G-2	NS			SOC-CO-1	10%
EN-HS-5	41%	CR-PP-1	NS			SOC-LC-10	10%
EN-CC-3	35%	CR-PP-4	NS			SOC-WO-3	10%
EN-W-4	35%	CR-PP-8	NS			SOC-SO-1	5%
EN-A-1	29%	CR-PP-9	NS			SOC-SO-2	5%
EN-A-2	29%	CR-PP-10	NS			SOC-VCA-3	5%
EN-W-7	29%						
EN-W-9	29%						
EN-NR-2	29%						
EN-NR-6	29%						
EN-NR-7	29%						
EN-A-3	24%						
EN-HS-2	24%						
EN-HS-7	24%						
EN-CC-5	18%						
EN-CC-6	18%						
EN-A-4	18%						
EN-CC-8	12%						
EN-A-5	12%						
EN-NR-3	12%						
EN-CC-4	6%						
EN-W-3	6%						

Table 7. Percentage of inclusion of the requirements of each sustainability pillar in the analysed policy initiatives

Environmental		Circularity		Economic		Social	
Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in European policies	Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in European policies	Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in European policies	Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in European policies
EN-CC-1	80%	CR-EoLS-1	27%	E-ER-1	40%	SOC-CO-1	0%
EN-CC-2	40%	CR-EoLS-2	20%	E-ER-2	20%	SOC-CO-2	53%
EN-CC-3	73%	CR-EoLS-3	73%	E-ER-3	27%	SOC-CO-3	47%
EN-CC-4	87%	CR-EoLS-4	0%	E-ER-4	7%	SOC-LC-1	0%
EN-CC-5	80%	CR-EoLS-5	7%	E-ER-5	13%	SOC-LC-2	0%
EN-CC-6	87%	CR-EoLS-6	60%	E-P-1	0%	SOC-LC-3	27%
EN-CC-7	20%	CR-EoLS-7	20%	E-P-2	13%	SOC-LC-4	13%
EN-CC-8	67%	CR-EoLS-8	20%	E-LTI-1	7%	SOC-LC-5	13%
EN-A-1	27%	CR-EoLS-9	53%	E-LTI-2	0%	SOC-LC-6	7%
EN-A-2	13%	CR-EoLS-10	7%	E-LTI-3	0%	SOC-LC-7	0%
EN-A-3	40%	CR-EoLS-11	7%	E-LTI-4	87%	SOC-LC-8	40%
EN-A-4	7%	CR-CBM-1	40%	E-LTI-5	20%	SOC-LC-9	7%
EN-A-5	0%	CR-CBM-2	27%	E-LTI-6	7%	SOC-LC-10	7%
EN-W-1	87%	CR-G-1	60%	E-PRF-1	0%	SOC-LC-11	0%
EN-W-2	53%	CR-G-2	0%	E-PRF-2	13%	SOC-LC-12	0%
EN-W-3	13%	CR-PP-1	73%	E-PRF-3	0%	SOC-SO-1	13%
EN-W-4	53%	CR-PP-2	13%	E-PRF-4	0%	SOC-SO-2	7%
EN-W-5	20%	CR-PP-3	40%	E-PRF-5	20%	SOC-SO-3	67%
EN-W-6	0%	CR-PP-4	7%	E-PRF-6	20%	SOC-VCA-1	20%
EN-W-7	0%	CR-PP-5	67%	E-PRF-7	0%	SOC-VCA-2	20%
EN-W-8	20%	CR-PP-6	0%	E-PRF-8	0%	SOC-VCA-3	27%
EN-W-9	0%	CR-PP-7	13%			SOC-VCA-4	0%
EN-W-10	13%	CR-PP-8	47%			SOC-VCA-5	7%
EN-S-1	80%	CR-PP-9	20%			SOC-VCA-6	0%
EN-S-2	13%	CR-PP-10	20%			SOC-WO-1	20%
EN-S-3	40%	CR-PP-11	7%			SOC-WO-2	7%
EN-B-1	33%	CR-PP-12	60%			SOC-WO-3	13%
EN-B-2	7%	CR-PMD-1	40%			SOC-WO-4	47%
EN-B-3	27%	CR-PMD-2	13%			SOC-WO-5	7%
EN-B-4	13%	CR-PMD-3	7%			SOC-WO-6	20%
EN-B-5	73%	CR-PMD-4	40%			SOC-WO-7	0%
EN-B-6	47%	CR-PMD-5	13%			SOC-WO-8	0%
EN-B-7	33%	CR-PMD-6	0%			SOC-WO-9	47%
EN-B-8	80%	CR-PMD-7	53%			SOC-WO-10	0%
EN-B-9	20%	CR-PMD-8	33%			SOC-WO-11	13%
EN-B-10	13%						
EN-NR-1	53%						
EN-NR-2	7%						
EN-NR-3	53%						
EN-NR-4	60%						
EN-NR-5	13%						
EN-NR-6	20%						
EN-NR-7	60%						
EN-HS-1	33%						
EN-HS-2	40%						
EN-HS-3	53%						
EN-HS-4	27%						
EN-HS-5	33%						
EN-HS-6	67%						
EN-HS-7	7%						
EN-G-1	87%						

Table 6. Normalised inclusion percentage (based on the maximum pillar value, IP) of the requirements in European policies. Ordered and prioritised as follows: Minimum Requirement if IP ≥ 50%, Intermediate if 50% < IP ≤ 20% and Advanced if IP < 20%.

Environmental		Circularity		Economic		Social	
Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in European policies	Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in European policies	Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in European policies	Requirement code	Inclusion ratio in European policies
EN-CC-4	100%	CR-EoLS-3	100%	E-LTI-4	100%	SOC-SO-3	100%
EN-CC-6	100%	CR-PP-1	100%	E-ER-1	46%	SOC-CO-2	80%
EN-W-1	100%	CR-PP-5	91%	E-ER-3	31%	SOC-CO-3	70%
EN-G-1	100%	CR-EoLS-6	82%	E-ER-2	23%	SOC-WO-4	70%
EN-CC-1	92%	CR-G-1	82%	E-LTI-5	23%	SOC-WO-9	70%
EN-CC-5	92%	CR-PP-12	82%	E-PRF-5	23%	SOC-LC-8	60%
EN-S-1	92%	CR-EoLS-9	73%	E-PRF-6	23%	SOC-LC-3	40%
EN-B-8	92%	CR-PMD-7	73%	E-ER-5	15%	SOC-VCA-3	40%
EN-CC-3	85%	CR-PP-8	64%	E-P-2	15%	SOC-VCA-1	30%
EN-B-5	85%	CR-CBM-1	55%	E-PRF-2	15%	SOC-VCA-2	30%
EN-CC-8	77%	CR-PP-3	55%	E-ER-4	8%	SOC-WO-1	30%
EN-HS-6	77%	CR-PMD-1	55%	E-LTI-1	8%	SOC-WO-6	30%
EN-NR-4	69%	CR-PMD-4	55%	E-LTI-6	8%	SOC-LC-4	20%
EN-NR-7	69%	CR-PMD-8	45%	E-P-1	0%	SOC-LC-5	20%
EN-W-2	62%	CR-EoLS-1	36%	E-LTI-2	0%	SOC-SO-1	20%
EN-W-4	62%	CR-CBM-2	36%	E-LTI-3	0%	SOC-WO-3	20%
EN-NR-1	62%	CR-EoLS-2	27%	E-PRF-1	0%	SOC-WO-11	20%
EN-NR-3	62%	CR-EoLS-7	27%	E-PRF-3	0%	SOC-LC-6	10%
EN-HS-3	62%	CR-EoLS-8	27%	E-PRF-4	0%	SOC-LC-9	10%
EN-B-6	54%	CR-PP-9	27%	E-PRF-7	0%	SOC-LC-10	10%
EN-CC-2	46%	CR-PP-10	27%	E-PRF-8	0%	SOC-SO-2	10%
EN-A-3	46%	CR-PP-2	18%			SOC-VCA-5	10%
EN-S-3	46%	CR-PP-7	18%			SOC-WO-2	10%
EN-HS-2	46%	CR-PMD-2	18%			SOC-WO-5	10%
EN-B-1	38%	CR-PMD-5	18%			SOC-CO-1	0%
EN-B-7	38%	CR-EoLS-5	9%			SOC-LC-1	0%
EN-HS-1	38%	CR-EoLS-10	9%			SOC-LC-2	0%
EN-HS-5	38%	CR-EoLS-11	9%			SOC-LC-7	0%
EN-A-1	31%	CR-PP-4	9%			SOC-LC-11	0%
EN-B-3	31%	CR-PP-11	9%			SOC-LC-12	0%
EN-HS-4	31%	CR-PMD-3	9%			SOC-VCA-4	0%
EN-CC-7	23%	CR-EoLS-4	0%			SOC-VCA-6	0%
EN-W-5	23%	CR-G-2	0%			SOC-WO-7	0%
EN-W-8	23%	CR-PP-6	0%			SOC-WO-8	0%
EN-B-9	23%	CR-PMD-6	0%			SOC-WO-10	0%
EN-NR-6	23%						
EN-A-2	15%						
EN-W-3	15%						
EN-W-10	15%						
EN-S-2	15%						
EN-B-4	15%						
EN-B-10	15%						
EN-NR-5	15%						
EN-A-4	8%						
EN-B-2	8%						
EN-NR-2	8%						
EN-HS-7	8%						
EN-A-5	0%						
EN-W-6	0%						
EN-W-7	0%						
EN-W-9	0%						

2.2.1 Analysis of the alignment of the requirements level of categorisation between standards and policies

As anticipated, the prerequisites prioritised by certification schemes and monitoring systems are analogous to those of policies. However, as evidenced by the preceding analyses of the Key Areas and Sub-Areas, it is also reasonable to conclude that there are discrepancies between the two, which can help to improve the results and the final definition of the minimum requirements. In fact, if the circularity and economic pillars are excluded from the comparison, since the study was not significant in the case of the standards (since aspects related to them have not yet been included), it can be observed that there is a great similarity in the distribution of the requirements in the three levels assigned to the environmental and social pillars.

Due to these differences in the results of the analyses, it is necessary to establish a set of criteria that will allow the final assignment of the level of enforceability of the requirements. These criteria have been proposed considering the political relevance of the regulatory framework and the likely evolution of the EU in the field of sustainability, as well as the certification experience and a pragmatic perspective on the standards that companies are able to achieve:

1. Requirements that have been classified as 'MR' in either of the two analyses will be designated as such. However, those that have been assigned an 'Advanced' level in the other analysis will be categorised as 'Intermediate' in the final assignment.
2. Those requirements whose categorisation is identical in both analyses are assigned directly to the level reached in these.
3. In case the requirement is categorised as 'Intermediate' in one of the analyses and 'Advanced' in the other, the latter prevails for the inclusion of the requirement in a longer timeframe.
4. In the absence of information from the standards, the level assigned to the requirements of the circularity and economic pillars is that of the policies.

In general terms, it can be stated that both standards and policies are aligned in terms of common objectives, defined by the sub-areas. In many cases, however, the specific actions prioritised to achieve these objectives differ. In order to achieve the laudable goals of climate neutrality, ecosystem conservation, sustainable resource consumption, economic growth and fair development, it is essential that the actors in the value chains implement the policies set out by the European Union. To facilitate this, environmental certification schemes should be aligned with these policies by requiring concrete measures for compliance.

Consequently, the proposed analysis provides a final framework based on the systematic study of both EU standards and policies in which the requirements that both CSLs and MSs should include in the short (minimum), medium (intermediate) and long term (advanced) are defined. The final assignment of levels to each requirement is shown in **Table 8**.

Table 8. Final categorisation of requirements based on the level of enforceability assigned after alignment of the standards and policy study. The requirements associated with acronyms can be found in Appendices A 1-4.

	Environmental	Circularity	Economic	Social
Minimum	CC-1, CC-2, CC-3 W-1, W-2, W-4, W-8 S-1 B-3, B-5, B-6, B-7, B-8, B-9 NR-1, NR-4, NR-7 HS-1, HS-3, HS-6, G-1			LC-5 SO-3 WO-1, WO-4, WO-6, WO-9, WO-11
Intermediate	CC-4, CC-5, CC-6, CC-7, CC-8 A-1, A-3 W-5 S-3 B-1, B-2, B-4, B-10 NR-3, NR-6 HS-2, HS-4, HS-5	Since the standards do not include meaningful information on these pillars, the enforceability associated with the requirements is given by the policy analysis. See Table 6 for the categorisation of the requirements into levels for the circularity and economic pillar.		CO-2, CO-3 LC-4, LC-8, LC-9 VCA-2 WO-5, WO-7
Advanced	A-2, A-4, A-5 W-3, W-6, W-7, W-9, W-10 S-2 NR-2, NR-5 HS-7			CO-1 LC-1, LC-2, LC-3, LC-6, LC-7, LC-10, LC-11, LC-12 SO-1, SO-2 VCA-1, VCA-3, VCA-4, VCA-5, VCA-6 WO-2, WO-3, WO-8, WO-10

2.3 Alignment of the minimum requirements of the BMS

The BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System has already undergone the initial phase of testing. However, it is important to note that this BMS is a work in progress, undergoing continuous refinement in collaboration with sister projects, including the STAR4BBS consortium. As a result, proposed changes are still being considered to assess the degree of coverage of the suggested requirements for the various sustainability pillars in the CSLs, as well as to ensure the presence of the most relevant requirements.

In order to collaborate on the refinement of the Content-Level, it has been proposed to align the analysis of this document with the BMS. In this way, the in-depth assessment of current European standards and policy initiatives applied to the monitoring system developed could help to ensure that all key requirements that a bio-based value chain must meet to be sustainable and circular are included in the standards for certification.

On this basis, those requirements considered to be minimum requirements, representing priority actions and current sustainability objectives, may be appropriate to include in the content level of the BMS in order to ensure full coverage of the most relevant aspects. To this end, the presence of the MRs identified for the four pillars in the monitoring system proposed has been assessed. Once evaluated, it has been observed that, in general terms, most of the minimum requirements are already included in the BMS.

Therefore, the fact that a new analysis, including policy initiatives, has been carried out and that the results are in line with those of the BMS, is a sign of the robustness of both the analysis carried out and the proposed monitoring system for assessing the sustainability and circularity of bio-based value chains. Going into more detail, of the 21 MRs identified for the environmental pillar, the BMS had already included 17 of these, while for the circularity pillar, 10 of the 13 identified had already been added. On the other hand, with regard to the economic pillar, the 2 MRs identified following the policy analysis were not taken into account in the BMS, while in the social pillar, the 7 identified minimum requirements were already included.

Thus, it is recommended to include the requirements EN-W-4, EN-B-6, EN-NR-1 and EN-G-1 in the environmental pillar of the BMS Content-Level, covering the following aspects respectively: the need for practices to improve water quality, to monitor and assess the environmental impact of the operation on biodiversity, to promote the sustainable use of abiotic resources (fossil fuels or materials of mineral origin) and to promote the training of operators in sustainable practices.

Regarding the circularity pillar, 3 MRs out of the 13 proposed have not yet been included in the monitoring system developed. Thus, it is recommended to add requirement CR-PP-3, which calls for the identification of strategies to reduce the use of fossil fuels, and CR-PMD-4, which requires products to be partially or completely biodegradable. Furthermore, although the BMS refers to the adoption of measures that favour recycling and the increase of circular flows as process inputs, it does not mention the adoption of practices to reduce and quantify the amount of waste generated in the process, and it is therefore recommended that requirement CR-EoLS-9 also be included.

Finally, for the economic pillar it is recommended to include requirement E-LTI-4, in which it is required to evaluate the use of economic resources in innovative strategies that improve the sustainability of the operation. Moreover, the necessity for evaluating long-term economic feasibility, as set forth in requirement E-ER-1, has also been proposed as a MR for incorporation into the Content Level. Although it narrowly failed to meet the criteria for inclusion, its relevance in mitigating economic risk and ensuring adherence to other requirements that safeguard economic and environmental sustainability of the process outweighs its potential value.

2.4 Assessment Metrics and Thresholds including Minimum Requirements: development of a Potential Scoring Framework

In this D3.2, apart from the identification of metrics and MRs, it is also proposed a scoring system to assess the degree of sustainability and circularity of the standards. In this way, this section proposes the metrics that could potentially be used to provide the users of the monitoring system with a reproducible method for assessing the level of sustainability associated with the CSLs, taking into account the categorisation of the requirements based on the level of enforceability associated with them and the fulfilment of those considered minimum as a threshold for a positive assessment of the standard.

Thus, taking as a starting point the scoring system currently under discussion within the consortium for the BMS, an alternative assessment methodology has been proposed that considers the level of enforceability associated with each requirement. In the Content-Level matrix proposed for D3.2, the terms 'criterion' and 'requirement' are analogous. However, in the BMS matrix, there may be multiple requirements within the same criterion. Therefore, in order to generalise the scoring system proposed from this

point onwards, the document will no longer refer to the requirement level of enforceability, as has been the case so far, but to the criterion.

The proposed metrics will give more relevance to those requirements that are considered more important for achieving sustainable development in the European context, based on regulations and standards, and to those that are more complex to implement. In this way, the criteria are classified and evaluated according to their level (enforceability) and typology (ambition-complexity), as explained in the following sections. In addition, a threshold has been proposed to be positively assessed based on the fulfilment of a percentage of the proposed minimum requirements.

2.4.1 Criterion level

The level of the criterion determines the degree of enforceability that is associated with that criterion, (those requirements that are considered to have a higher relevance in the framework of sustainability should be mandatorily included in certification schemes and labels). Such criteria will be considered as "minimum requirements" as they should be applied generically to all standards to be considered robust and will therefore be credited with 1 point.

On the other hand, the Content Level includes criteria with a lower relevance within the European normative framework or in the standards, consequently, the inclusion of these criteria in the schemes and labels is considered optional and is attributed a lower degree of enforceability within the monitoring system ("intermediate" and "advanced"). Taking this into account, the inclusion of these criteria in the standards demonstrates a higher degree of commitment and is therefore attributed a higher score, 2 points for intermediate and 3 points advanced.

2.4.2 Criterion type

In both Content-Level (BMS and the proposed on D3.2) the requirements identified during the information gathering phase were categorised on the basis of their typology, i.e. considering their orientation and assessment approach. Accordingly, a homologous classification has been established for the criteria of both MS distinguishing between:

- **Policy-based:** criteria that focus on the company's policies, plans and related strategies. These requirements assess how well operators adhere to and implement sustainability policies and plans.
- **Practice-based:** criteria that focus on specific practices and actions that an organisation implements in its day-to-day operations. They assess the implementation of sustainable practices in the company's operations.
- **Impact-based:** criteria that evaluate the concrete results and impacts an organization has in terms of sustainability. They focus on measuring and reducing negative impacts and increasing positive impacts on social, environmental, and economic aspects.

In this case, the score assigned to each type of criterion is based on the ambition or complexity of implementing them, as mentioned above. Thus, criteria based on policies are considered the least ambitious in terms of implementation, those based on practices somewhat more complex, and those based on impact assessment the most ambitious, with scores of 1, 2 and 3 points respectively.

2.4.3 Allocation of points to each criterion

Table 9 summarises the allocation of points according to the level and type of criterion, so that a criterion can have a minimum of 0 points (not met) and a maximum of 6 if it is advanced and impactful.

Table 9. Allocation of points according to the fulfilment of the criterion and its level and typology

Level	Not conforming	Minimum	Intermediate	Advanced
Score – criteria		1	2	3
Type	0	Policy	Practice	Impact
Score – type		1	2	3

Table 10 shows the score assigned if the criterion is met according to its level and typology.

Table 10. Total points allocation according to the level and typology of the criterion

Type/Level	Minimum	Intermediate	Advanced
Policy	2	3	4
Practice	3	4	5
Impact	4	5	6

However, it is possible that the criterion is only partially fulfilled if it consists of more than one requirement. Consequently, its score will also be partial on this basis. If a criterion consists of 4 requirements and only 2 of them are fulfilled, the final score for this criterion will be 50% of the maximum score it would receive for fulfilling half of these requirements. **Equation [1]** shows the equation used to assign the score for the criterion.

$$Score_{Criterion} = (Level_{Score} + Type_{Score}) \cdot \frac{N^{\circ} \text{ of requirements fulfilled}}{Total N^{\circ} \text{ of requirements}} \quad [1]$$

2.4.4 Assessment of each pillar individually

Each pillar has a different number of criteria, the sum of the maximum points assigned to each of them according to their level and typology determine the highest score that can be achieved in the pillar. The same applies for each Key Area separately.

In this way, for each pillar, the degree of compliance with the pillar can be assessed by the ratio between the score achieved and the maximum possible score (**Equation [2]**), as well as that of the Key Areas or principles (in the case of the BMS), taking into account the maximum score assigned to each one and the sum of the criteria fulfilled on this (**Equation [3]**). This allows for an overall assessment of each pillar identifying the main weaknesses of the standard and a detailed assessment of Key Area to identify possible gaps or specific omissions.

$$Score_{Pillar} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Score_{Criterion,i}}{Maximum\ score\ of\ the\ pillar} \quad [2]$$

$$Score_{Key\ Area} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n Score_{Criterion,j}}{Maximum\ score\ of\ the\ Key\ Area} \quad [3]$$

Note that if the standard does not include a particular Key Area in its certification scheme, it must be excluded from the final assessment, provided that adequate justification is given for its exclusion. In this way, standards that focus on the certification of specific areas are not disadvantaged.

The percentage score achieved defines the degree of performance overall and for each pillar and Key Area of the standard. **Table 11** shows the assessment assigned according to the score achieved, and the different assessments have been colour-coded.

Table 11. Evaluation based on the score achieved by the standard, applies to the overall evaluation as well as to each pillar and each Key Area.

Percentage score achieved	Assigned assessment
100 – 75 %	Very good
75 – 50 %	Good
50 – 25 %	Pass
< 25 %	Need to improve

On the other hand, in order to avoid a positive assessment of certification schemes or labels that do not comply with the basic minimum requirements common to all standards, a threshold/barrier has been established to prevent this. This threshold requires compliance with at least 50% of the minimum requirements established for the pillars and Key Areas, which means that otherwise the standard cannot achieve a score higher than 50% (with a final assessment of Pass).

Figure 9 shows a spider graph with the overall percentages of conformity of an aleatory certification scheme against the criteria of each pillar of the Content-Level matrix of the D3.2. In addition, **Figure 10-Figure 13** show the degree of conformity with respect to each Key Area of the different pillars.

Figure 9. Overall performance of the standard in the 4 pillars of sustainability

Figure 10. Performance of the standard in the different Key Areas of the environment pillar

Figure 11. Performance of the standard in the different Key Areas of the economic pillar.

Figure 12. Performance of the standard in the different Key Areas of the social pillar.

Figure 13. Performance of the standard in the different Key Areas of the circularity pillar.

Table 12 shows the results in numerical format for the four content-level pillars. Furthermore, **Table 13** shows the level of compliance for the different Key Areas of the environmental pillar as an example.

Table 12. Summary of the standard's performance against the 4 pillars of sustainability and the fulfilment of minimum requirements.

Pillar	N° of MR ¹	N° of MR fulfilled	% of MR compliance (%MRC)	Meets the threshold? (%MRC ≥ 50%)	Maximum score	Score achieved	Overall Score _{Pillar}	Performance Level
Environmental	21	14	67%	Y	190	113	59%	Good
Circularity	13	7	54%	Y	155	68	44%	Pass
Economic	2	0	0%	N²	92	49	53%	Pass
Social	7	6	86%	Y	145	109	75%	Very good

¹MR = Minimum requirements; ²Red indicates that the MR threshold has not been met and that the 'Performance Level' cannot exceed 'Pass'.

Table 13. Summary of the standard's performance against the different Key Areas of the environmental pillar and how it is meeting their minimum requirements.

Key Area	N° of MR	N° of MR fulfilled	MR compliance (%MRC)	Meets the threshold? (%MRC ≥ 50%)	Maximum score	Score achieved	Overall Score _{Pillar}	Performance Level
Climate change	3	3	100 %	Y	32	26	81%	Very good
Air	0	0	N/A ¹	N/A	19	12	63%	Good
Water	2	1	50 %	Y	38	24	63%	Good
Soil	1	0	0 %	N	11	4	36%	Pass
Biodiversity	6	4	67 %	Y	34	12	35%	Pass
Natural resources	3	2	67 %	Y	29	12	41%	Pass
Hazardous substances	3	2	67 %	Y	24	20	83%	Very good
Generic	1	1	100%	Y	3	3	100%	Very good

¹N/A = Not applicable

3 System Level minimum requirements

Another important component of the BMS is the system level that assesses the robustness, as a key indicator of a certification scheme’s trustworthiness. The system level characteristics focus on the operational requirements of the certification scheme, including its governance and the development process of standards.

In total 4 categories and 17 principles have been suggested to be included in the system level (SL), with 64 criteria, totalling 64 indicators (**Figure 14**).

Figure 14. Structure of the system level classification with corresponding numbers per element

The names of the categories, as well as the principles, criteria, and requirements, underwent multiple stages of review, revision, and updating following their initial development. In deliverable D3.2 of STAR4BBS, the initial preselected system-level elements were presented. Stakeholder input and feedback served as the foundation for these changes, leading to the development of new elements used during the first testing phase of the BMS. Although significant changes have already been made at this stage, the system-level elements remain subject to further revisions following the second testing phase. All updates are communicated with stakeholders, whose input is actively sought and valued.

Category	Principle
Governance and Scheme management	Scheme objectives and impacts
	Governance structure
	Stakeholder participation
	Complaints and dispute resolution mechanism
	Monitoring and evaluation
Standard setting	Standards content and structure
	Standard-setting process
	Standards consultation
Assurance	Assurance system
	Conformity assessment
	Conformity assessment bodies
	Auditing
	Oversight mechanism
Traceability and claims	CoC traceability system
	Claims and products labelling policy
	Consequences of misuse of claims
	Minimum percentage claims

Out of the 64 requirements, with the help of stakeholders (in co-creation workshops and internal meetings), a short set of requirements - called minimum requirements - has been proposed. The idea is to try to prioritize some requirements as “need to have” requirements and others as “nice to know”. The selection and performance levels of these minimum requirements will be subjected to change over time based on stakeholder inputs, policy benchmarks, and ongoing assessments.

3.1 Methodology

The methodology for determining the proposed minimum requirements involved several key steps:

The minimum requirements, or “need to have” indicators, are those that schemes/labels have to meet to be deemed robust.

The set of newly proposed minimum requirements was initially obtained only by marking those SL indicators that were pre-selected by stakeholders during co-creation workshop and other internal and external events (project meetings, conference side events, etc). Tools used for collecting stakeholders’ feedback included Mentimeter and chat options, as well as live discussions. This was later combined with a comparison of the Siegelklarheit tool’s minimum requirements. Siegelklarheit was one of the six tools selected for an in-depth analysis in *D1.4 Report on existing monitoring schemes with recommendations for new system*. Since this tool has a similar evaluation structure to the conceptualized structure of the BMS and leverages data for the ITC Standards Map (which the system level is building on), we decided to cross-check the minimum requirements of Siegelklarheit with the ones selected by internal and external stakeholders.

At a later stage, during the revision of SL indicators, but also of the minimum requirements of the SL, a layer of policy benchmarking was added, focusing on the RED II and EU Green Claims Directive. These two policies were chosen as they set out (to a certain degree) detailed requirements on the aspects of the operational system of the schemes (e.g. for biofuels within the framework of the RED). This process ensured that the system-level criteria were adequately covered by relevant policies. Instances where criteria were not covered by these policies, but were deemed essential based on stakeholder feedback, have remained selected.

Ultimately, stakeholder feedback as a variable had the biggest influence on the selection of the minimum requirements, to ensure their robustness and practicality for sustainability certification schemes and labels.

The process of proposing minimum requirements is shown in detail in Appendix C (Tables Table D.1-Table D.4). For each of the four categories (Governance and Scheme Management, Standard setting, Assurance, Traceability, and Claims), the criteria coverage was benchmarked against the aforementioned variables.

Coverage by policies was explained in the Legend below the tables, indicating full coverage – marked with a green cell (considered as sufficiently similar as the requirement itself), partial mention – yellow cell (text implies that the requirement is covered to some degree, but not fully), or no coverage (red cell).

Within the first phase of minimum requirements proposal process (pre-selection), more weight was given to the stakeholders' selection compared to the Siegelklarheit's minimum requirements, due to different objectives of the mentioned tool in contrast to the BMS. Proposed minimum requirements in the last column were thus marked as green bold "x".

For the second phase - through discussions with experts, it has been concluded that the minimum requirements should further include all requirements mandated by RED II, anticipating that the EU policymakers (one of the target audiences of the BMS) might reference these criteria for broader biomass regulation, i.e. in application for non-energy sectors. While the Green Claims Directive (GCD) is still under negotiation, initial reviews suggest it does not set high stringency level requirements, so criteria not covered by this policy were not excluded (more weight was given to the RED II). Proposed minimum requirements in the last column were thus marked as black bold "x".

As the Tables in Appendix D show, there are instances where none of the criteria matched the benchmarking variables (e.g. *The scheme owner proactively encourages participation in standard-setting of all stakeholders directly affected*), or where only GCD or Siegelklarheit covered it (e.g. *The scheme owner shall ensure that participation in the standard-setting process is open to all stakeholders*). The decision for inclusion or exclusion of such requirements was done on a case-by-case basis, after taking into account experts' opinion and opportunistic literature coverage of the topic.

The following sub-section outlines the proposed set of the minimum requirements for the system level, following a description of the four SL.

Governance and Scheme Management

Governance and Scheme Management encompass a certification system's organizational and managerial aspects. This category involves the definition of the scheme's objectives and intended impacts, ensuring clarity and focus on desired sustainability outcomes. It includes the governance structure, which provides the necessary legal, technical, and operational framework to maintain the scheme's impartiality and independence. Stakeholder participation is key in this area, ensuring that relevant groups are involved in decision-making and implementation processes. Additionally, this category covers the mechanisms for handling complaints and disputes, as well as the ongoing monitoring and evaluation of the scheme's performance to ensure continuous improvement.

The proposed 7 minimum requirements for the governance and scheme management indicators are shown below:

Governance and Scheme Management	
Scheme objectives and impacts	The scheme has sustainability-defined goals.
Governance structure	The scheme owner makes its organizational structure available.
	The scheme owner is economically independent from the certificate holder.
Stakeholder participation	The procedures of the top decision-making body ensure that there is a balanced representation of stakeholder interests, where no single interest predominates.
Complaints and dispute resolution mechanism	The scheme owner has a publicly available complaints mechanism in place for appealing decisions and resolving disputes.
	The scheme owner enables complaints procedures to include appeal mechanisms that are open to any involved party.
Monitoring and evaluation	There is a system in place for monitoring and evaluation (M&E).

Standard setting

Standard Setting involves the development, organization, and revision of the criteria and guidelines within a standard, as well as its improvement over time. This category includes the content and structure of the standards, ensuring they are comprehensive and well-organized. The standard-setting process is methodical, incorporating systematic approaches to create and update standards. Consultation with stakeholders is a crucial component, ensuring that the standards are relevant, balanced, and reflective of diverse interests. This participatory process helps maintain the credibility and relevance of the standards.

The proposed 4 minimum requirements for the standard-setting indicators are shown below:

Standard Setting	
Standard-setting process	The scheme owner reviews and revises the standards at least once every 5 years.
Standards consultation	Standards setting and update is subjected to public consultation.
	The scheme owner shall ensure that participation in the standard-setting process is open to all stakeholders.
	The scheme owner ensures balanced participation of stakeholder interests in the consultation and decision-making processes.

Assurance

Assurance provides a systematic framework for assessing compliance with standards, designed to ensure that all entities and processes within a certification system meet established standards. It encompasses documented procedures, regular reviews, and mechanisms for overseeing and verifying compliance. This category includes the assessment of conformity, where specific bodies (conformity assessment bodies) are responsible for evaluating whether the standards are being met. Assurance also involves auditing, a thorough and independent examination to confirm adherence to standards, and an oversight mechanism that supervises the performance of these bodies to ensure the integrity and reliability of the assurance system.

The proposed 9 minimum requirements for the assurance indicators are shown below:

Assurance	
Assurance system	The scheme provides a documented assessment methodology for CABs to assess compliance with the standard.
	The scheme owner requires CABs to have a documented complaints mechanism in place for compliance decisions.
	The scheme owner ensures that summary certification/verification reports are made available.
Conformity assessment	Minimum level of conformity assessment allowed by the scheme owner.
	The scheme owner requires CABs to have a procedure in place for how clients are required to address non-conformities, including when a certificate or license is suspended or revoked.
Conformity assessment bodies (CABs)	The scheme owner requires CABs to be compliant with and accredited according to ISO/IEC 17065, ISO/IEC 17021, ISO/IEC 17020, or equivalent.
	The scheme owner makes (or requires the Oversight Body (OB) to make) public a list of all accredited/approved CABs.
	The scheme owner requires specific qualifications and competencies for auditors of conformity assessment bodies (CABs).
Oversight mechanism	The scheme owner requires a documented oversight of assurance activities and assurance providers.

Traceability and Claims

Traceability and Claims focus on the transparency aspects of a certification system, and how certification information is maintained. This category includes the Chain of Custody (CoC) and traceability system, which track products through various stages of the supply chain, ensuring that certified products can be traced back to their origin. It also involves

the policies and guidelines for making claims and labelling products, ensuring that claims are accurate and substantiated by certification. Measures for addressing the misuse of claims are included, ensuring that any fraudulent or misleading claims are appropriately handled. Additionally, this category covers the minimum content percentage required for products to make certain claims, ensuring that the use of certification labels is both meaningful and trustworthy.

The proposed 8 minimum requirements for the traceability and claims indicators are shown below:

Traceability and Claims	
CoC traceability system	The scheme has a documented Chain of Custody (CoC) standard or other traceability requirements for checking product flow between links of the supply chain.
	The scheme owner requires CoC CABs to be compliant with ISO/IEC 17020, ISO/IEC 17021, or ISO/IEC 17065.
	The scheme owner has or requires CABs to have documented procedures for CoC auditing methods and frequency.
	The scheme owner requires CABs to verify that all enterprises within the chain maintain and keep accurate and accessible traceability records.
Claims and products labelling policy	Claims and labelling requirements ensure that claims or logos clearly indicate to what they apply.
	The label is accompanied by an explanatory text claim or a link to further information.
	Claims requirements specify the types of claims that can be made for different types of CoC models, where the scheme owner allows for more than one model.
Consequences of misuse of claims	The scheme owner has a procedure in place that defines specific consequences of misuse of claims.

4 Conclusions

This report has identified a set of minimum requirements that might be adequate to be included as a part of the BMS, to ensure robustness and effectiveness of the CSLs and consistency with European objectives and priorities for the development of a sustainable bioeconomy. Most of them are already included showing the current BMS robustness. In addition, based on this analysis, a scoring system has been proposed to contribute to the development of an evaluation structure of the BMS.

In this way, the in-depth study of the priorities of the 19 certification schemes and 12 monitoring systems previously analysed in D3.2, as well as 15 policy initiatives identified in D1.1, has made it possible to categorise sustainability requirements (relevant for the Content-Level of the BMS) proposed in deliverable D3.2 based on their level of enforceability. The greater the number of times a standard or policy refers to a particular requirement, the greater the enforceability associated with it.

Regarding the Content-Level requirements, it has been observed that the trends of both CSLs and MSs are similar, with very similar priorities in the different Key Areas proposed. With regard to the environmental sustainability criteria, both CSLs and MSs prioritise aspects related to the conservation and restoration of soil, water, biodiversity and the correct management and use of hazardous substances, while for the social pillar they focus on the conditions and rights of workers and local communities. On the other hand, it has also been observed that, while covering a significant part of the sustainability aspects necessary to fully cover multiple sectors of the bioeconomy, it has become apparent that most of them leave key points of the Areas uncovered. The latter is much more acute concerning the economic and circularity pillar, the requirements of which have hardly been included in the CSLs and MSs analysed.

On the other hand, in order to address these gaps identified in the standards and to identify those requirements that should be included immediately in order to align with the EU's sustainable development objectives, an analysis of policy initiatives was carried out. It was found that the level of coverage of the sustainability aspects included in the four pillars was higher than in the CSLs and MSs, but that there was still significant room for improvement in certain Key Areas. Therefore, it is recommended to review those requirements that were not rated as MR and assess their inclusion in future policy initiatives and standards.

The 142 requirements included in the four pillars of the Content-Level were categorised based on their level of enforceability, obtained according to their frequency of appearance in the documents analysed, resulting in the following distribution: 43 minimum requirements (21 environmental, 13 circularity, 2 economic and 7 social), 39 intermediate (18, 8, 5 and 8 respectively) and 60 advanced (12, 14, 14, 14 and 20 respectively). Finally, this categorisation was used to articulate the evaluation structure and the proposal of metrics.

The minimum requirements of the system level of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System are essential for assessing the robustness and credibility of the certification systems. These requirements are a subset of the pre-selected indicators among all proposed principles of the system level, and their fulfilment is necessary for a scheme or a label to be considered reliable. Out of 64 currently existing system-level indicators, 28 are proposed as minimum (or “need to have”) requirements - 7 for the Governance and Scheme management category; 4 for Standard setting; 9 for Assurance; and 8 for Traceability and claims category. It is expected that these numbers will change over time, with advancements in policy updates as well as in iteration of the whole BMS.

5 Appendix

A.1 Requirements identification codes for the environmental pillar

ENVIRONMENTAL PILLAR

Key Area - Climate change	
EN-CC-1	The certification scheme shall require having a plan/policy in place on GHG emissions, mitigation strategies and adaptation measures to climate change.
EN-CC-2	The certification scheme shall require quantifying lifecycle GHG emissions and specify the methodology that should be followed.
EN-CC-3	The certification scheme requires GHG emissions to be reduced between specified periods.
EN-CC-4	The certification scheme shall require operators to implement "Carbon neutrality" in their operation activities.
EN-CC-5	The certification scheme shall include requirements to maintain or increase carbon stocks
EN-CC-6	The certification scheme shall require implementing climate adaptation activities
EN-CC-7	The certification scheme shall require that biomass is not produced on land with high carbon stocks through specific policies and practices.
EN-CC-8	The certification scheme shall require monitoring and management of High Carbon Stock areas

Key Area - Air	
EN-A-1	The certification scheme shall require a plan on air pollution
EN-A-2	The certification scheme shall include a requirement to monitor emissions over time
EN-A-3	The certification scheme shall require implementing strategies to avoid and/or reduce air pollution emissions
EN-A-4	The certification scheme shall set threshold values for air emissions and reduction targets
EN-A-5	The certification scheme shall include requirements on open-air burning

Key Area - Water	
EN-W-1	The certification scheme shall include requirements to prevent surface water and ground water contamination
EN-W-2	The certification scheme shall require the monitoring and impact assessment of the quality of surface and/or ground water
EN-W-3	The certification scheme shall require set targets for emissions of pollutants to water
EN-W-4	The certification scheme shall require practices to improve water quality
EN-W-5	The certification scheme shall require a water management plan is in place and periodically reviewed
EN-W-6	The certification scheme shall require operators to document their relevant and up-to-date permits related to water use

EN-W-7	The certification scheme shall require sustainable water extraction practices
EN-W-8	The certification scheme shall require water use reduction practices
EN-W-9	The certification scheme shall include requirements to manage water use in areas of scarcity or high risk
EN-W-10	The certification scheme shall require assessing the risks and impacts on water usage

Key Area - **Soil**

EN-S-1	The certification scheme shall require practices that conserve and enhance soil quality
EN-S-2	The certification scheme shall require operators to have a soil management plan on place and regularly review it
EN-S-3	The certification scheme shall require operators monitor and assess impacts on soil

Key Area - **Biodiversity**

EN-B-1	The certification scheme shall include requirements to regulate the access and use of wildlife species and native flora
EN-B-2	The certification scheme shall include requirements on the appropriate use and management of genetically modified organisms (GMOs)
EN-B-3	The certification scheme shall include requirements on the use of alien invasive species
EN-B-4	The certification scheme shall require practices to protect rare, threatened or endangered wildlife species
EN-B-5	The certification scheme shall require operators have a plan on biodiversity conservation
EN-B-6	The certification scheme shall require monitoring and assessing the impact on biodiversity
EN-B-7	The certification scheme shall require operators to implement strategies and actions of spatial management to protect ecosystems
EN-B-8	The certification scheme shall require operators to implement practices to restore or rehabilitate natural habitats and/or ecosystems
EN-B-9	The certification scheme shall include requirements to ensure legally protected and internationally recognized protected areas are respected
EN-B-10	The certification scheme shall include requirements to ensure High Conservation Value Areas are protected

Key Area – **Natural resources**

EN-NR-1	The certification scheme shall include requirements on sustainable consumption of abiotic resources
EN-NR-2	The certification scheme shall require assessing iLUC Risk
EN-NR-3	The certification scheme shall require practices to maintain and/or enhance ecosystem functions and services
EN-NR-4	The certification scheme shall require sustainable management practices of biotic resources

EN-NR-5	The certification scheme shall require operators have a plan/policy on sustainable management of biotic resources
EN-NR-6	The certification scheme shall require operators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of resource management
EN-NR-7	The certification scheme shall require operators to use of sustainably sourced resources

Key Area – Hazardous substances

EN-HS-1	The certification scheme shall require assessing the impact on human health of the business activities
EN-HS-2	The certification scheme shall require a waste and by-product management plan
EN-HS-3	The certification scheme shall include requirements for waste management
EN-HS-4	The certification scheme shall require sustainable pest control practices
EN-HS-5	The certification scheme shall require sustainable fertilization
EN-HS-6	The certification scheme shall require practices that use hazardous chemicals in a selective and targeted manner
EN-HS-7	The certification scheme shall require a plan on the use of hazardous chemicals

Key Area - Generic

EN-G-1	The certification scheme shall require operators to receive instruction and training in sustainable practices
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A.2 Requirements identification codes for the circularity pillar

CIRCULARITY PILLAR

Key Area – End-of-life-stage

CR-EoLS-1	The certification scheme shall require a policy management plan on reusing or recycle wastewater
CR-EoLS-2	The certification scheme shall require operators to manage their agricultural co-products and waste
CR-EoLS-3	The certification scheme shall require operators to separate and recycle waste
CR-EoLS-4	The certification scheme shall distinguish between type of residues
CR-EoLS-5	The certification scheme shall require the re-use or recycle waste on-site
CR-EoLS-6	The certification scheme shall include criteria/requirements to improve process circularity
CR-EoLS-7	The certification scheme shall require the quantification of the total non-valorised waste generated per unit of product and useful co-product
CR-EoLS-8	The certification scheme shall require monitoring and measuring the amount of disposable products and implementing measures for reducing them

CR-EoLS-9	The certification scheme shall include criteria to take actions in order to reduce waste on the production phase
CR-EoLS-10	The certification scheme shall require quantifying the discards
CR-EoLS-11	The certification scheme shall require the identification and evaluation of the amount of unsold finished goods and their management

Key Area – **Circular business model**

CR-CBM-1	The certification scheme shall require identification of strategies between process schemes to promote industrial symbiosis
CR-CBM-2	The certification scheme shall include criteria on circularity business models

Key Area – **Generic**

CR-G-1	The certification scheme shall require a strategic plan on circularity
CR-G-2	The certification scheme shall require companies to report on circularity activities

Key Area – **Production processes**

CR-PP-1	The certification scheme shall require measures to increase the use of recycled and renewable materials
CR-PP-2	The certification scheme shall require quantifying the percentage of bio-based material and placing a threshold value
CR-PP-3	The certification scheme shall require quantifying the percentage of fossil resources used in the activity, considering both materials and energetic sources
CR-PP-4	The certification scheme shall require the quantification of the energy intensity
CR-PP-5	The certification scheme shall require the quantification of the percentage of renewable energies used
CR-PP-6	The certification scheme shall require calculating the natural origin percentage
CR-PP-7	The certification scheme shall require measuring the circularity of the process (e.g., material circularity index)
CR-PP-8	The certification scheme shall require measurements on the use of secondary raw materials as input resources
CR-PP-9	The certification scheme shall require the quantification of the recovery materials used in the process
CR-PP-10	The certification scheme shall require the compliance with the required technical and product specification of the materials recycled
CR-PP-11	The certification scheme shall require the quantification of the amount of feedstock required for production.
CR-PP-12	The certification scheme shall require operators to establish, implement and maintain an appropriate system to improve energy efficiency. It shall include the identification of technologies and equipment to improve energy efficiency in the process and savings targets

Key Area – Products and materials design

CR-PMD-1	The certification scheme shall require operators to implement strategies to extend the life of the products and materials produced
CR-PMD-2	The certification scheme shall require operators to provide additional lifetime guarantee for the product beyond the legal obligations
CR-PMD-3	The certification scheme shall require the measurement of the degree of renewability of the product
CR-PMD-4	The certification scheme shall require products and materials to meet specific criteria regarding biodegradability, easy disintegration, and the potential for composting
CR-PMD-5	The certification scheme shall require guidelines for consumers on how to dispose of the bio-based product
CR-PMD-6	The certification scheme shall require evaluating the product circularity
CR-PMD-7	The certification scheme shall require operators implement circularity strategies on their products and materials designs
CR-PMD-8	The certification scheme shall require operators to identify and implement circularity strategies on packaging products

A.3 Requirements identification codes for the economic pillar

ECONOMIC PILLAR
Key Area – Economic risks

E-ER-1	The certification scheme shall require operators to document and quantify all the economic related items to evaluate the long-term economic viability of the process
E-ER-2	The certification scheme shall require operators to document and assess risks from natural hazards (e.g., climate change, drought)
E-ER-3	The certification scheme shall require operators to identify and implement strategies and action plans to reduce possible economic risks
E-ER-4	The certification scheme shall require operators to have an economic strategic plan
E-ER-5	The certification scheme shall require the quantification of the feedstock capacity and availability for maintaining process productivity

Key Area – Productivity

E-P-1	The certification scheme shall require operators to perform of techno-economic analysis and productivity evaluation
E-P-2	The certification scheme shall require the quantification of production efficiency and productivity (economic output per unit of input) of a unit operation

Key Area – Long-term investment

E-LTI-1	The certification scheme shall require operators to quantify the fixed capital investment in relation with the plant capacity
E-LTI-2	The certification scheme shall require operators to quantify the economic resources used for improving economic sustainability
E-LTI-3	The certification scheme shall require operators to document and identify the economic fundings received

E-LTI-4	The certification scheme shall require operators to document and identify the economic expenditures on innovation and sustainable strategies
E-LTI-5	The certification scheme shall require operators to document and identify the participation on collaborative investments
E-LTI-6	The certification scheme shall require operators to quantify the discounted payback period and return on investment financial metrics

Key Area – Profitability	
E-PRF-1	The certification scheme shall require the documentation and quantification of yields, costs, incomes (net income and gross income) and profitability of the production process or product
E-PRF-2	The certification scheme shall require the evaluation of possibilities of new market and economic activities related with all relevant good and services of the process, product or facility
E-PRF-3	The certification scheme shall require quantification of how revenues may be affected by environmental life-cycle costs (e.g., emissions costs)
E-PRF-4	The certification scheme shall require the development of a life-cycle-cost analysis following the ISO 15686-5:2017
E-PRF-5	The certification scheme shall require the documentation and quantification of the business expectation of future profit, on job stability and long-term perspectives of the business model
E-PRF-6	The certification scheme shall require the quantification of the capacity of creating revenues by feedstocks coming from renewable resources
E-PRF-7	The certification scheme shall require the monitoring and quantification of feedstock availability to increase production capacity
E-PRF-8	The certification scheme shall require the quantification of the minimum feedstock capacity requirement to achieve a positive net present value over the useful life of the facility

A.4 Requirements identification codes for the social pillar

SOCIAL PILLAR

Key Area – Consumers	
SOC-CO-1	The certification scheme shall require the presence of a mechanism for customers to provide feedback
SOC-CO-2	The certification scheme shall require compliance with the relevant health and safety standard and inclusion of evidence communicating this to the client
SOC-CO-3	The certification scheme shall require operators to comply with regulations regarding transparency and that there have been no consumer complaints regarding transparency

Key Area – Local community	
SOC-LC-1	The certification scheme shall have requirements on impact assessment local communities' access to resources, such as electricity, water, land, sanitation, forest, etc
SOC-LC-2	The certification scheme shall require operators that grievance and resolution mechanisms are documented
SOC-LC-3	The certification scheme shall require operators to document the communication and consultation mechanism they have in place
SOC-LC-4	The certification scheme shall require operators to report policies and/or implementation of activities that contribute to their social development

SOC-LC-5	The certification scheme shall require measures taken to address local employment, including indigenous peoples
SOC-LC-6	The certification scheme shall require a growth in the market share of the company
SOC-LC-7	The certification scheme shall require the respect and protect traditional and cultural production practices
SOC-LC-8	The certification scheme shall require management measures to promote the long-term health and well-being of the communities affected by its activity
SOC-LC-9	The certification scheme shall require documentation demonstrating legal rights to manage the land as forests and manage and utilise its resources
SOC-LC-10	The certification scheme shall require that operators to establish compensation and benefits mechanisms for individuals affected by involuntary resettlement, physical displacement, or economic displacement resulting from business operations. Alternatively, operators must develop and implement an action plan specifically designed to address compensation and benefits for displaced persons
SOC-LC-11	The certification scheme shall require the identification of indigenous people that may be affected by management activities
SOC-LC-12	The certification scheme shall require the description of programmes and practices to determine and manage the effects of company activities on local population in conflict-affected or high- risk areas. Alternatively, the certification scheme shall require criteria on using independent expertise to assess human rights violations risks/policies

Key Area – **Society**

SOC-SO-1	The certification scheme shall require operators to have a policy on poverty alleviation in place, implemented and regularly review it
SOC-SO-2	The certification scheme shall consider the diversification of benefits and/or products to strengthen the local economy proportionate to the scale and intensity of management activities
SOC-SO-3	The certification scheme shall require measures to improve and ensure local food security or an assessment on impact on this to identify and reduce risks

Key Area – **Value chain actors**

SOC-VCA-1	The certification scheme shall require have criteria on fair competition
SOC-VCA-2	The certification scheme shall require the operators to have strategies and policies in place designed to enhance the social and economic standing of women producers within the producer operation, as well as any disadvantaged or discriminated groups in the local community
SOC-VCA-3	The certification scheme shall require operators to have a mechanism of intellectual protection in place
SOC-VCA-4	The certification scheme shall include criteria the regarding supplier relationships (written contracts with traders to be issued, advance payments request, establishing specific delivery times for suppliers and processes for late delivery, claim procedures), as well as establish an agreement to maintain long-term trade relationships
SOC-VCA-5	The certification scheme shall require operators to have clear contractual agreements or commitments in place which specify the amount and other terms around practices to enhance wealth distribution
SOC-VCA-6	The certification scheme shall require monitoring and reporting on price premiums and other fairtrade activities

Key Area – Workers

SOC-WO-1	The certification scheme shall require compliance with the minimum age for work as defined by applicable national legal requirements or the age of completion of compulsory education, or the prohibition of child labour
SOC-WO-2	The certification scheme shall require operators to have legal contracts in written form, presented in languages comprehensible to workers, especially in cases of low literacy
SOC-WO-3	The certification scheme shall require operators to have formal formats or templates for labour contracts to define all rights and obligations of workers
SOC-WO-4	The certification scheme shall include criteria on equal opportunities or discrimination
SOC-WO-5	The certification scheme shall require that wages of workers are paid regularly, meet or exceed at least legal, industry minimum standards or, where applicable, collective bargaining agreements, and compensation for overtime or legal wage deductions
SOC-WO-6	The certification scheme shall require operators to implement measures to safeguard rights relating to forced labour, considering both physical or psychological violence against workers
SOC-WO-7	The certification scheme shall include requirements on freedom of association and the right to collective bargaining
SOC-WO-8	The certification scheme shall include criteria on mental and physical abuse, including sexual harassment
SOC-WO-9	The certification scheme shall require the presence of adequate protection measures are in place to ensure that the workers safety is guaranteed
SOC-WO-10	The certification scheme shall require operators to provide incentives, including paid leaves, medical care, paid vacations
SOC-WO-11	The certification scheme shall have requirements related to: working hours and rest periods; worker representation and communication; training; overtime compensation; flexible working conditions; grievance mechanisms

Table B.1. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level environment requirements in the 19 analysed certification schemes and labels. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.1. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	RSB Global Advanced Products Certification	ISCC Plus	OK Biobased	Bio-Based Content	REDcert ²	Green Gold Label	Better Biomass	OK Compost	OK Biodegradable	Cradle to Cradle	Rainforest Alliance	Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC)	ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard	GoodWeave	Green Button	COSMOS	Fair for Life	Fairtrade International	
EN-CC-1																				
EN-CC-2																				
EN-CC-3																				
EN-CC-4																				
EN-CC-5																				
EN-CC-6																				
EN-CC-7																				
EN-CC-8																				
EN-A-1																				
EN-A-2																				
EN-A-3																				
EN-A-4																				
EN-A-5																				
EN-W-1																				
EN-W-2																				
EN-W-3																				
EN-W-4																				
EN-W-5																				
EN-W-6																				
EN-W-7																				
EN-W-8																				
EN-W-9																				
EN-W-10																				
EN-S-1																				
EN-S-2																				
EN-S-3																				
EN-B-1																				
EN-B-2																				
EN-B-3																				
EN-B-4																				
EN-B-5																				
EN-B-6																				
EN-B-7																				
EN-B-8																				
EN-B-9																				
EN-B-10																				
EN-NR-1																				
EN-NR-2																				
EN-NR-3																				
EN-NR-4																				
EN-NR-5																				
EN-NR-6																				
EN-NR-7																				
EN-HS-1																				
EN-HS-2																				
EN-HS-3																				
EN-HS-4																				
EN-HS-5																				
EN-HS-6																				
EN-HS-7																				
EN-G-1																				

Table B.2. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level environmental requirements in the 12 analysed monitoring systems. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.1. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	STAR ProBio Sustainability Certification Tools (SCT)	STAR ProBio Integrated Assessment Tool (IAT)	SUMINISTRO	ADVANCEFUEL	Textile Exchange Corporate Fiber & Materials Benchmark (CFMB)	FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool	SSCI Benchmarking and Recognition (Sustainable Supply Chain Initiative)	WWF Certification Assessment Tool	GSSI Global Benchmark Tool	ITC Standards Maps	GIZ Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool (SSCT) and Siegelklarheit	SME Compass
EN-CC-1	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-CC-2	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-CC-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-CC-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-CC-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-CC-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-CC-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-CC-8	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-A-1	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-A-2	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
EN-A-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
EN-A-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-A-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-W-1	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
EN-W-2	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-W-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red
EN-W-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-W-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red
EN-W-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-W-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-W-8	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
EN-W-9	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-W-10	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
EN-S-1	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-S-2	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-S-3	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-B-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red
EN-B-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red
EN-B-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red
EN-B-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red
EN-B-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-B-6	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-B-7	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-B-8	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-B-9	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-B-10	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-NR-1	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
EN-NR-2	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-NR-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-NR-4	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red
EN-NR-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red
EN-NR-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red
EN-NR-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red
EN-HS-1	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red
EN-HS-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
EN-HS-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
EN-HS-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-HS-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-HS-6	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red
EN-HS-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-G-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red

Table B.3. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level circularity requirements in the 19 analysed certification schemes and labels. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.2. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	RSB Global Advanced Products Certification	ISCC Plus	OK Biobased	Bio-Based Content	REDcert ²	Green Gold Label	Better Biomass	OK Compost	OK Biodegradable	Cradle to Cradle	Rainforest Alliance	Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC)	ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard	GoodWeave	Green Button	COSMOS	Fair for Life	Fairtrade International
CR-EoLS-1	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-2	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-4	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-8	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-9	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-10	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-11	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-CBM-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-CBM-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-G-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-G-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-2	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-3	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
CR-PP-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
CR-PP-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-8	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-9	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-10	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-11	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-12	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
CR-PMD-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
CR-PMD-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-8	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red

Table B.4. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level circularity requirements in the 12 analysed monitoring systems. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.2. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	STAR ProBio Sustainability Certification Tools (SCT)	STAR ProBio Integrated Assessment Tool (IAT)	SUMINISTRO	ADVANCEFUEL	Textile Exchange Corporate Fiber & Materials Benchmark (CFMB)	FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool	SSCI Benchmarking and Recognition (Sustainable Supply Chain Initiative)	WWF Certification Assessment Tool	GSSI Global Benchmark Tool	ITC Standards Maps	GIZ Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool (SSCT) and Siegelklarheit	SME Compass
CR-EoLS-1												
CR-EoLS-2												
CR-EoLS-3												
CR-EoLS-4												
CR-EoLS-5												
CR-EoLS-6												
CR-EoLS-7												
CR-EoLS-8												
CR-EoLS-9												
CR-EoLS-10												
CR-EoLS-11												
CR-CBM-1												
CR-CBM-2												
CR-G-1												
CR-G-2												
CR-PP-1												
CR-PP-2												
CR-PP-3												
CR-PP-4												
CR-PP-5												
CR-PP-6												
CR-PP-7												
CR-PP-8												
CR-PP-9												
CR-PP-10												
CR-PP-11												
CR-PP-12												
CR-PMD-1												
CR-PMD-2												
CR-PMD-3												
CR-PMD-4												
CR-PMD-5												
CR-PMD-6												
CR-PMD-7												
CR-PMD-8												

Table B.5. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level economic requirements in the 19 analysed certification schemes and labels. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.3. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	RSB Global Advanced Products Certification	ISCC Plus	OK Biobased	Bio-Based Content	REDcert ²	Green Gold Label	Better Biomass	OK Compost	OK Biodegradable	Cradle to Cradle	Rainforest Alliance	Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC)	ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard	GoodWeave	Green Button	COSMOS	Fair for Life	Fairtrade International
E-ER-1		Green																	
E-ER-2																			
E-ER-3																			
E-ER-4																			
E-ER-5																			
E-P-1																			
E-P-2																			
E-LTI-1																			
E-LTI-2											Green	Green							
E-LTI-3					Green														
E-LTI-4																			
E-LTI-5																			
E-LTI-6																			
E-PRF-1		Green																	
E-PRF-2													Green						
E-PRF-3																			
E-PRF-4																			
E-PRF-5																			
E-PRF-6																			
E-PRF-7																			
E-PRF-8																			

Table B.6. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level economic requirements in the 12 analysed monitoring systems. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.3. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	STAR ProBio Sustainability Certification Tools (SCT)	STAR ProBio Integrated Assessment Tool (IAT)	SUMINISTRO	ADVANCEFUEL	Textile Exchange Corporate Fiber & Materials Benchmark (CFMB)	FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool	SSCI Benchmarking and Recognition (Sustainable Supply Chain Initiative)	WWF Certification Assessment Tool	GSSI Global Benchmark Tool	ITC Standards Maps	GIZ Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool (SSCT) and Siegelklarheit	SME Compass
E-ER-1												
E-ER-2												
E-ER-3												
E-ER-4												
E-ER-5												
E-P-1												
E-P-2												
E-LTI-1												
E-LTI-2												
E-LTI-3												
E-LTI-4												
E-LTI-5												
E-LTI-6												
E-PRF-1												
E-PRF-2												
E-PRF-3												
E-PRF-4												
E-PRF-5												
E-PRF-6												
E-PRF-7												
E-PRF-8												

Table B.7. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level social requirements in the 19 analysed certification schemes and labels. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.4. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	RSB Global Advanced Products Certification	ISCC Plus	OK Biobased	Bio-Based Content	REDcert ²	Green Gold Label	Better Biomass	OK Compost	OK Biodegradable	Cradle to Cradle	Rainforest Alliance	Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC)	ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard	GoodWeave	Green Button	COSMOS	Fair for Life	Fairtrade International	
SOC-CO-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-CO-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
SOC-CO-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-LC-1	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-2	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-LC-5	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-LC-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-8	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-9	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-LC-10	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-11	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-12	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-SO-1	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-SO-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-SO-3	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-VCA-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-VCA-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-VCA-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-VCA-4	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-VCA-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-VCA-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-1	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-2	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-WO-4	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-5	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-6	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-7	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-8	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-9	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-10	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green
SOC-WO-11	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green

Table B.8. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level social criteria in the 12 analysed monitoring systems. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.4. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	STAR ProBio Sustainability Certification Tools (SCT)	STAR ProBio Integrated Assessment Tool (IAT)	SUMINISTRO	ADVANCEFUEL	Textile Exchange Corporate Fiber & Materials Benchmark (CFMB)	FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool	SSCI Benchmarking and Recognition (Sustainable Supply Chain Initiative)	WWF Certification Assessment Tool	GSSI Global Benchmark Tool	ITC Standards Maps	GIZ Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool (SSCT) and Siegelklarheit	SME Compass
SOC-CO-1	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-CO-2	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-CO-3	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
SOC-LC-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red
SOC-LC-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-LC-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-LC-5	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-LC-6	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-LC-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-LC-8	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
SOC-LC-9	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red
SOC-LC-10	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-LC-11	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red
SOC-LC-12	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-SO-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-SO-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-SO-3	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
SOC-VCA-1	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
SOC-VCA-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-VCA-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
SOC-VCA-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-VCA-5	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-VCA-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-1	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
SOC-WO-4	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-5	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-8	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-9	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-10	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red
SOC-WO-11	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red

C. Review of the number of policies that include the proposed requirements for further categorisation.

Table C.1. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level environment requirements in the policy initiatives/ Directives analysed from D1.1. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.1. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	EU Bioeconomy Action Plan	Circular Economy Action Plan	First EU Taxonomy Delegated Act	EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities	European Green Deal	Waste Framework Directive	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation	European Climate Law	Proposal for a Revision of the Land Use, Forestry and Agriculture Regulation	EU Updated Bioeconomy Strategy	Soil Strategy for 2030	Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy	Sustainable carbon cycles	Farm to Fork Strategy	Biodiversity Strategy for 2030
EN-CC-1	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
EN-CC-2	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-CC-3	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red
EN-CC-4	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
EN-CC-5	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
EN-CC-6	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
EN-CC-7	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green
EN-CC-8	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
EN-A-1	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-A-2	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-A-3	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green
EN-A-4	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-A-5	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-W-1	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green
EN-W-2	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red
EN-W-3	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red
EN-W-4	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green
EN-W-5	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-W-6	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-W-7	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-W-8	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-W-9	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-W-10	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-S-1	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
EN-S-2	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
EN-S-3	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green
EN-B-1	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-B-2	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-B-3	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-B-4	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-B-5	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-B-6	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-B-7	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-B-8	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-B-9	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-B-10	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-NR-1	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-NR-2	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-NR-3	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-NR-4	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-NR-5	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-NR-6	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-NR-7	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-HS-1	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-HS-2	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
EN-HS-3	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-HS-4	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-HS-5	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-HS-6	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-HS-7	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
EN-G-1	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green

Table C.2. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level circularity requirements in the policy initiatives/ Directives analysed from D1.1. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.2. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	EU Bioeconomy Action Plan	Circular Economy Action Plan	First EU Taxonomy Delegated Act	EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities	European Green Deal	Waste Framework Directive	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation	European Climate Law	Proposal for a Revision of the Land Use, Forestry and Agriculture Regulation	EU Updated Bioeconomy Strategy	Soil Strategy for 2030	Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy	Sustainable carbon cycles	Farm to Fork Strategy	Biodiversity Strategy for 2030
CR-EoLS-1	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-2	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red
CR-EoLS-3	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red
CR-EoLS-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-6	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red
CR-EoLS-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
CR-EoLS-8	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-9	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red
CR-EoLS-10	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-EoLS-11	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-CBM-1	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-CBM-2	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
CR-G-1	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red
CR-G-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-1	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red
CR-PP-2	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
CR-PP-3	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green
CR-PP-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-5	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green
CR-PP-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-7	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-8	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red
CR-PP-9	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-10	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-11	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PP-12	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red
CR-PMD-1	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-2	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-3	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-4	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-7	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red
CR-PMD-8	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red

Table C.3. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level economic requirements in the policy initiatives/ Directives analysed from D1.1. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.3. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	EU Bioeconomy Action Plan	Circular Economy Action Plan	First EU Taxonomy Delegated Act	EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities	European Green Deal	Waste Framework Directive	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation	European Climate Law	Proposal for a Revision of the Land Use, Forestry and Agriculture Regulation	EU Updated Bioeconomy Strategy	Soil Strategy for 2030	Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy	Sustainable carbon cycles	Farm to Fork Strategy	Biodiversity Strategy for 2030
E-ER-1	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-ER-2	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-ER-3	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red
E-ER-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-ER-5	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-P-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-P-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
E-LTI-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-LTI-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-LTI-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-LTI-4	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
E-LTI-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-LTI-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
E-PRF-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-PRF-2	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-PRF-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-PRF-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-PRF-5	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-PRF-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red
E-PRF-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
E-PRF-8	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red

Table C.4. Results of the frequency analysis of the content level social requirements in the policy initiatives/ Directives analysed from D1.1. The requirements with their codes are available in appendix A.4. Colour code: green (included), red (not included)

Requirement code	EU Bioeconomy Action Plan	Circular Economy Action Plan	First EU Taxonomy Delegated Act	EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities	European Green Deal	Waste Framework Directive	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation	European Climate Law	Proposal for a Revision of the Land Use, Forestry and Agriculture Regulation	EU Updated Bioeconomy Strategy	Soil Strategy for 2030	Sustainable carbon cycles	Farm to Fork Strategy	Biodiversity Strategy for 2030
SOC-CO-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-CO-2	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red
SOC-CO-3	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-LC-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-3	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
SOC-LC-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-5	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-8	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
SOC-LC-9	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
SOC-LC-10	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-11	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-LC-12	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-SO-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-SO-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red
SOC-SO-3	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
SOC-VCA-1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-VCA-2	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-VCA-3	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-VCA-4	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-VCA-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-VCA-6	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-WO-1	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red
SOC-WO-2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-WO-3	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-WO-4	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green
SOC-WO-5	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red
SOC-WO-6	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red
SOC-WO-7	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-WO-8	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-WO-9	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	Green	Red
SOC-WO-10	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
SOC-WO-11	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red

D. Minimum requirements selection for the System Level

Table D.1. Minimum requirements selection for the Standard Setting category. Colour code meaning at the end of the appendix D

Category	Principle	Criteria	Green Claims Directive	RED II requirements	REDII Assessment Protocol	Siegelklarheit	Stakeholders selection	Proposed	
Standard setting	Standards content and structure	The scheme owner makes consultation drafts and final versions of its standards freely available and easily accessible in the scheme's official languages.							
		The standard document contains requirements that support achievement of the defined sustainability outcomes.							
		The scheme owner ensures that guidance is in place to support consistent interpretation of the standard.							
	Standard-setting process	The scheme owner reviews and revises the standards at least once every 5 years.							X
		The scheme owner makes available the standard-setting procedures or a public summary of how stakeholders can engage.							
	Standards consultation	Standards setting and update is subjected to public consultation.							X
		The scheme owner shall ensure that participation in the standard-setting process is open to all stakeholders.							X
		The scheme owner proactively encourages participation in standard-setting of all stakeholders directly affected.							
		The scheme owner ensures balanced participation of stakeholder interests in the consultation and decision-making processes.							X
		The scheme owner ensures that procedures and guidance are in place for adaptation or interpretation of the standard to regional contexts.							
		The scheme owner provides information on how the input received from stakeholder consultations has been included in the final version of the standard.							

Table D.2. Minimum requirements selection for the Assurance category. Colour code meaning at the end of the appendix D

Category	Principle	Criteria	Green Claims Directive	RED II requirements	REDII Assessment Protocol	Siegelklarheit	Stakeholders selection	Proposed
Assurance	Assurance system	The scheme provides a documented assessment methodology for CABs to assess compliance with the standard.						X
		The scheme owner reviews their assurance system on a regular basis.						
		The scheme owner requires CABs to have a documented complaints mechanism in place for compliance decisions.						X
		The certificate or license defines the scope of assurance.						
		The scheme owner ensures that summary certification/verification reports are made available.						X
	Conformity assessment	Minimum level of conformity assessment allowed by the scheme owner.						X
		The scheme owner requires CABs to have a procedure in place for how clients are required to address non-conformities, including when a certificate or license is suspended or revoked.						X
		The scheme owner defines guidelines for decision-making to ensure that CABs use consistent procedures for determining compliance of clients with the standard.						
	Conformity assessment bodies	The scheme owner requires CABs to be compliant with and accredited according to ISO/IEC 17065, ISO/IEC 17021 or ISO/IEC 17020.						X
		The scheme owner makes (or requires the Oversight Body (OB) to make) public a list of all accredited/approved CABs.						X
		The scheme owner maintains or requires CABs to maintain a publicly accessible list of certified products/product groups and certified/verified enterprises.						
		The scheme owner requires specific qualifications and competencies for auditors of conformity assessment bodies (CABs).						X
	Auditing	The scheme owner defines frequency of a full audit process.						
		The scheme owner defines the type of activities CABs are required to undertake during a full audit.						
		The scheme owner requires or allows CABs to do unscheduled audits.						
	Oversight mechanism	The scheme owner requires a documented oversight of assurance activities and assurance providers.						X
		The scheme owner requires oversight bodies to have a publicly available documented complaints mechanism in place for compliance decisions.						

Table D.3. Minimum requirements selection for the Traceability and Claims category. Colour code meaning at the end of the appendix D

Category	Principle	Criteria	Green Claims Directive	RED II requirements	REDII Assessment Protocol	Siegelklarheit	Stakeholders selection	Proposed
Traceability	CoC traceability system	The scheme has a documented Chain of Custody (CoC) standard or other traceability requirements for checking product flow between links of the supply chain.						X
		The scheme owner requires all enterprises that are physically handling the certified product to undergo a CoC audit if the product can be destined for retail sale as a certified, labeled product.						
		The scheme owner requires CoC CABs to be compliant with ISO/IEC 17020, ISO/IEC 17021, or ISO/IEC 17065.						X
		The scheme owner defines which activities are CoC CABs required to undertake during a full CoC assessment.						
		The scheme owner has or requires CABs to have documented procedures for CoC auditing methods and frequency.						X
		The scheme defines procedures for CoC certification of multiple sites of one or several legal entities.						
		The scheme owner requires subcontractors to meet the CoC requirements.						
		The scheme has a clear statement in case mixing of certified with uncertified inputs is allowed.						
		Continuous increase of the amount of certified input is encouraged, in case of mixing.						
		The scheme owner requires CABs to verify that all enterprises within the chain maintain and keep accurate and accessible traceability records.						
	Claims and products labelling policy	Scheme provides description of its specific policies for products labelling and claims use.						
		Claims and labelling requirements ensure that claims or logos clearly indicate to what they apply.						X
		The label is accompanied by an explanatory text claim or a link to further information.						X
		Claims and label users are required to use unique license numbers or other tracking mechanisms.						
		Claims requirements specify the types of claims that can be made for different types of CoC models, where the scheme owner allows for more than one model.						X
		The scheme owner specifies requirements for claims depending on the percentage of certified / verified content in a product.						
	Consequences of misuse of claims	The scheme owner has a procedure in place that defines specific consequences of misuse of claims.						X
		The scheme owner requires surveillance of the accurate use of claims and labels in the market.						
	Minimum percentage claims	The scheme defines the minimum percentage of a certified / verified input in a single ingredient product for a claim to be allowed for that product.						
		The scheme defines the minimum percentage of certified / verified material in a composite product for a claim to be allowed for that product.						

Table D.4. Minimum requirements selection for the Governance and Scheme Management category. Colour code meaning at the end of the appendix D

Category	Principle	Criteria	Green Claims Directive	RED II requirements	REDII Assessment Protocol	Siegelklarheit	Stakeholders selection	Proposed
Governance and Scheme management	Scheme objectives and impacts	The scheme has sustainability-defined goals.	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	X
		The scheme owner ensures measuring of scheme's impacts and progress towards its sustainability goals.	Yellow	Red	Red	Red	Red	
	Governance structure	The scheme owner is a legal entity, or an organization that is a partnership of legal entities, or a government or inter-governmental agency.	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Green	Red	
		The scheme owner make its organizational structure available.	Green	Red	Green	Green	Green	X
		The scheme owner is economically independent from the certificate holder.	Red	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	X
		The top decision-making body members are accountable to all stakeholders.	Yellow	Red	Red	Red	Red	
		The scheme owner makes quantitative information on the income sources or financing structure of the scheme available.	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red	
	Stakeholder participation	Stakeholders have the possibility to participate in or provide formal input on the scheme governance.	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	
		The procedures of the top decision-making body ensure that there is a balanced representation of stakeholder interests, where no single interest predominates.	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Red	Green	X
		The scheme owner addresses engagement of under-represented stakeholder groups.	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	
		The scheme owner ensures that clients and other affected stakeholders are notified of any changes to any scheme components that might affect them.	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	
	Complaints and dispute resolution mechanism	The scheme owner has a publicly available complaints mechanism in place for appealing decisions and resolving disputes.	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	X
		The scheme owner enables complaints procedures to include appeal mechanisms that are open to any involved party.	Green	Red	Green	Red	Red	X
	Monitoring and evaluation	There is a system in place for monitoring and evaluation (M&E).	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	X
		The scheme owner makes sustainability results from M&E publicly available.	Red	Red	Green	Red	Red	
		The scheme owner uses the results of monitoring and evaluation for learning and improvement of its standards.	Red	Red	Yellow	Red	Red	

Legend:

Red	The requirement is not met
Yellow	The requirement is covered by the policy document to some extent, but not enough to be considered as being met
Green	The requirement is entirely met by the policy document

6 References

1. ADVANCEFUEL project. ADVANCEFUEL monitoring system. Retrieved from <http://www.advancefuel.eu/>
2. Aquaculture Stewardship Council. ASC-MSC seaweed standard. Retrieved from <https://asc-aqua.org/producers/asc-standards/seaweed-standard/>
3. Auld, G., Gulbrandsen, L. H., & McDermott, C. L. (2008). Certification schemes and the impacts on forests and forestry. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 33(1), 187-211. doi:10.1146/annurev.enviro.33.013007.103754
4. Better Biomass. Better biomass certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://betterbiomass.nl/en/certification/>
5. COSMOS. COSMOS certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://www.cosmos-standard.org/en/certification/>
6. Cradle to Cradle Products Innovation Institute. Cradle to cradle certified® standard. Retrieved from <https://c2ccertified.org/the-standard>
7. European Commission. (2018a). Bioeconomy: The european way to use our natural resources action plan. Retrieved from <https://europanel.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/COM-Bioeconomy-Action-Plan-2018.pdf>
8. European Commission. (2018b). COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A sustainable bioeconomy for europe: Strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52018DC0673>
9. European Commission. (2019). The european green deal. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/ES/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2019%3A640%3AFIN>
10. European Commission. (2020a). COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A farm to fork strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0381>
11. European Commission. (2020b). COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 bringing nature back into our lives. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52020DC0380>
12. European Commission. (2020c). A new circular economy action plan for a cleaner and more competitive europe. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A98%3AFIN>
13. European Commission. (2021a). COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2021/2139 of 4 june 2021 (first EU taxonomy delegated act). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/ES/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32021R2139>
14. European Commission. (2021b). COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL sustainable carbon cycles. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0800>
15. European Commission. (2021c). COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS EU soil strategy for

- 2030 reaping the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0699>
16. European Commission. (2021d). COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS on a new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU transforming the EU's blue economy for a sustainable future. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0240>
 17. European Commission. (2021e). Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL amending regulations (EU) 2018/841 as regards the scope, simplifying the compliance rules, setting out the targets of the member states for 2030 and committing to the collective achievement of climate neutrality by 2035 in the land use, forestry and agriculture sector, and (EU) 2018/1999 as regards improvement in monitoring, reporting, tracking of progress and review. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0554>
 18. European Commission. (2022). Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing a framework for setting ecodesign requirements for sustainable products and repealing directive 2009/125/EC. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0142>
 19. European Parliament and the council of the European Union. (2020). REGULATION (EU) 2020/852 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 18 June 2020 (EU taxonomy for sustainable activities). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/ES/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R0852>
 20. Fair for Life. Fair for life certification scheme. Retrieved from https://www.fairforlife.org/pmws/indexDOM.php?client_id=fairforlife&page_id=home
 21. Fairtrade International. Fairtrade international sustainability label. Retrieved from <https://www.fairtrade.net/>
 22. FEFAC and ITC. FEFAC responsible soy benchmarking tool. Retrieved from [https://fefac.eu/newsroom/news/launch-of-soy-benchmarking-tool-for-fefac-soy-sourcing-guidelines-2021/#:~:text=The%20Soy%20Benchmarking%20Tool%20is,joint%20UN%20and%20WTO%20agency\).](https://fefac.eu/newsroom/news/launch-of-soy-benchmarking-tool-for-fefac-soy-sourcing-guidelines-2021/#:~:text=The%20Soy%20Benchmarking%20Tool%20is,joint%20UN%20and%20WTO%20agency).)
 23. Forest Stewardship Council International. FSC certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://fsc.org/en>
 24. Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative. GSSI global benchmark tool. Retrieved from <https://ourgssi.org/benchmarking/>
 25. GoodWeave International. GoodWeave standard. Retrieved from <https://goodweave.org/about/goodweave-label/>
 26. Green Button. Green button certification label for sustainable textiles. Retrieved from <https://gruener-knopf.de/en>
 27. Green Gold Label Foundation. GGL certification scheme for sustainable biomass. Retrieved from <https://greengoldlabel.com/>
 28. International Sustainability & Carbon Certification. ISCC PLUS certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://www.iscc-system.org/>
 29. International Trade Center. ITC standards maps. Retrieved from <https://intracen.org/resources/tools/standards-map>

30. Mori Junior, R., Franks, D. M., & Ali, S. H. (2016). Sustainability certification schemes: Evaluating their effectiveness and adaptability. *Corporate Governance*, 16(3), 579-592. doi: 10.1108/CG-03-2016-0066
31. NEN.Bio-based content certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://biobasedcontent.eu/>
32. Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification.PEFC certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://www.pefc.org/>
33. Rainforest Alliance.Rainforest alliance certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://www.rainforest-alliance.org/>
34. REDcert GmbH.REDCert² certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://www.redcert.org/en/>
35. RSB.Roundtable on sustainable biomaterials association certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://rsb.org/certification/certification-schemes/rsb-global-advanced-products-certification/>
36. Siegelklarheit GIZ sustainability standards comparison tool (SSCT) and siegelklarheit. Retrieved from https://www.siegelklarheit.de/static/media/SGK_Factsheet-SSCT_EN_RK%20NEU.pdf
37. SME Compass.SME compass monitoring system. Retrieved from <https://kompass.wirtschaft-entwicklung.de/en/>
38. Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Bio-based Products. (a). STAR ProBio integrated assessment tool (IAT). Retrieved from <http://www.star-probio.eu/research/>
39. Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Bio-based Products. (b). STAR ProBio sustainability certification tools (SCT). Retrieved from <http://www.star-probio.eu/research/>
- 40.The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. (2018). Directive 2008/98/EC of the european parliament and of the council of 19 november 2008 on waste and repealing certain directive (waste framework directive). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2008/98/oj/eng>
41. The european Parliament and the Council of the European Union. (2021). Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of the european parliament and of the council of 30 june 2021 establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending regulations (EC) no 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999 ('European climate law'). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32021R1119>
42. Tröster, R., & Hiete, M. (2018). Success of voluntary sustainability certification schemes – A comprehensive review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 196, 1034-1043. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.05.240
43. TÜV AUSTRIA Belgium. (a). OK biobased certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://www.tuv-at.be/okcert/certifications/ok-biobased/>
44. TÜV AUSTRIA Belgium. (b). OK compost certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://www.tuv-at.be/okcert/certifications/ok-compost-seedling-real/>
45. TÜV AUSTRIA Belgium.OK biodegradable certification scheme. Retrieved from <https://www.tuv-at.be/okcert/certifications/ok-biodegradable/>
46. World Wide Fund for Nature.STANDARD: WWF certification assessment tool (CAT). Retrieved from https://wwf.panda.org/wwf_news/?228430/WWF-Certification-Assessment-Tool-CAT

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